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**Nourishing the Mind: Exploring the Gut-Anxiety Axis in Paediatric
Mental Health**

By

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Abstract

The possible link between children's anxiety, gut-microbiota, and diet has drawn more attention in recent years. This review paper centers on three key aspects: the influence of dietary imbalances on anxiety symptoms, the significance of gut microbiota composition, and the effectiveness of nutritional interventions in alleviating anxiety symptoms within the paediatric population. This paper offers a thorough evaluation of 16 studies, which encompass cross-sectional, longitudinal, and interventional research methods. It investigates the potential link between diet, gut microbiota, and anxiety symptoms in children and adolescents, relying on existing evidence. The findings indicate a consistent relationship where a healthier diet, rich in fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, is associated with lower anxiety levels in this age group. In contrast, dietary imbalances have been linked to heightened anxiety symptoms among children and adolescents.

Moreover, the review examines the possible connection between gut microbiota disturbances and anxiety symptoms. Nonetheless, there is still insufficient evidence to validate the effectiveness of nutritional interventions in alleviating anxiety. The analysis highlights significant limitations in the current studies, such as the prevalence of cross-sectional designs and variations in measurement techniques. It emphasizes the need for more robust longitudinal studies to establish causal relationships and evaluate the long-term effects of nutritional interventions on anxiety in children. Additionally, the paper suggests future research pathways, stressing the importance of standardized methodologies and larger, more diverse sample populations, while also proposing the development of innovative and comprehensive approaches for addressing paediatric anxiety. In conclusion, this review enhances the understanding of the interactions between nutrition, gut-microbiota, and mental health in children, setting the stage for further investigation and potential clinical applications.

Keywords: Paediatric anxiety, gut-microbiota, nutrition, gut-brain axis, nutritional psychiatry, mental health, dietary interventions.

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CHAPTER 1

Nourishing the Mind: Exploring the Gut-Anxiety Axis in Paediatric Mental Health

Anxiety disorders rank among the most prevalent mental health issues faced by children and adolescents (Connolly & Bernstein, 2007). In recent years, there has been a notable rise in the global prevalence of anxiety disorders, impacting roughly four percent of the worldwide population (Javaid et al., 2023). This trend raises alarm for younger demographics, as there has been a significant uptick in diagnoses among children and adolescents over the last decade (CDC, 2023). By 2020, approximately 5.6 million children had been diagnosed with various anxiety disorders (Osorio, 2022). Regrettably, many instances remain undiagnosed and untreated (Connolly & Bernstein, 2007), and existing anxiety treatments frequently pose negative side effects for children, underscoring the necessity for innovative solutions (Ipser et al., 2009).

Recognizing this, researchers have increasingly explored the connection between diet and mental health, establishing that food choices significantly influence neurobiology and overall mental wellness (O'Neil et al., 2014). Consequently, scholars have concentrated on how consistent dietary practices may lead to the emergence of anxiety disorders and associated symptoms, particularly over the last decade (Eliby et al., 2023). This interest is in line with the expanding field of nutritional psychiatry, which investigates how nutrients and eating behaviours affect mental health outcomes (Sarris et al., 2019). Evidence indicates that dietary patterns play a crucial role in brain function and development, affecting behaviour, emotional regulation, and cognitive abilities (Jacka, 2010). Thus, the connection between the gut and the brain, termed the gut-brain axis, is recognized as a significant factor in this context (Merlo et al., 2024). The gut-microbiota, a complex community of microorganisms residing in the digestive system, has been shown to influence brain function and behaviour through several mechanisms, including neuroinflammation, neurotransmitter production, and immune system modulation (Xiong et al., 2023). Studies indicate that alterations in the composition of the gut microbiota may contribute to the onset of mental health disorders, such as anxiety (Asbjornsdottir et al., 2022).

In this regard, paediatric nutritional psychiatry is gaining traction as it seeks to investigate the connections between diet, gut microbiota, and anxiety symptoms in children. The American Psychological Association (APA, 2013) notes that anxiety in children can adversely affect their mental health, social growth, and academic success. This condition arises from various factors, including genetics, environmental influences, and nervous system interactions (Eley et al., 2012). Provided that, grasping the gut-anxiety axis holds important consequences for clinical practice.

Exploring the intricate connections among paediatric anxiety, changes in gut microbiota, and dietary factors could aid in creating novel approaches to improve mental health and reduce the effects of anxiety disorders. Within the realm of clinical psychology, studies focused on the links between nutrition, gut microbiota, and paediatric anxiety have significant implications. Traditionally, the treatment of anxiety disorders in children has been predominantly focused on psychotherapy and medication (Creswell et al., 2020). Yet, by exploring how dietary practices and gut health impact mental health, we can open doors to more comprehensive and complementary treatment strategies (Marx et al., 2017) by delving into the intricate links among nutrition, the gut-brain axis, and anxiety symptoms in young people. There is potential to develop non-invasive interventions that may be better received by patients and their families. Integrating nutritional factors into the evaluation and treatment of paediatric anxiety can empower clinical psychologists to augment the effectiveness of their strategies and offer a more thorough method of patient care.

As a result, this paper adds to the growing field of psychiatry dietary, which seeks to elucidate the role dietary factors play in mental health outcomes (Jacka, 2017). For health professionals, integrating nutritional psychiatry principles is particularly beneficial, since the dietary patterns established in childhood can have long-lasting effects on both physical and mental health throughout an individual's life (Vereijken et al., 2011). By integrating traditional clinical psychology with the emerging field of nutritional psychiatry, this research has the potential to transform the approaches for understanding, evaluating, and treating paediatric anxiety. The holistic and interdisciplinary perspective advocated in this review could promote the creation of more tailored and effective interventions that address the complex nature of anxiety and related mental health issues faced by children and adolescents. This could ultimately contribute to the promotion of their overall well-being. It is therefore imperative to conduct an in-depth examination of the scientific literature pertaining to the intricate

interrelationship between neurobiology, nutrition and childhood anxiety. A comprehensive grasp of this pivotal subject matter will shed light on the field and facilitate the formulation of pioneering strategies to enhance the mental well-being of the most vulnerable demographic: children.

1. Theoretical Background

1.1 Nutritional Psychiatry

Nutritional psychiatry is often referred to as the "mood-food" science (Munson, (2023)). It is an emerging area of study that investigates the complex connections between dietary habits, specific nutrients, and mental well-being (Sarris et al., 2019). This field highlights the bidirectional relationship between nutrition and brain health, demonstrating how dietary choices can influence emotional health. A significant concept in this area is the effect of inflammation on mental well-being. Studies suggest that elevated inflammation levels are associated with diets high in processed foods, refined carbohydrates, and unhealthy fats, which appear to increase the risk of mental health issues (Berk et al., 2013). Researchers argue that a nutrient-dense diet can positively affect the brain's production of these critical agents, leading to a decrease in anxiety and other mental health disorders (Jacka et al., 2010). For example, the SMILE study (Jack et al., 2017) provided evidence that adjusting one's diet can serve as a practical and effective approach to tackling common mental health issues and related concerns. Thus, nutritional psychiatry recognizes the potential of dietary changes to influence neurobiological mechanisms involved in psychiatric conditions (Sarris et al., 2019).

This idea is based on the understanding that the brain, being highly metabolically active, requires a sufficient supply and balance of nutrients (Contreras-Rodriguez et al., 2022). Adequate nutrition is vital for proper cognitive, emotional, and behavioural development in children during critical growth phases (Prado & Dewey, 2014). On the other hand, unbalanced diets that involve high consumption of processed foods, insufficient intake of essential nutrients, and disparities in macro- and micronutrient consumption can heighten the risk of mental health issues among youth (Contreras-Rodriguez et al., 2022). In fact, research has identified a correlation between certain nutritional factors, such as eating patterns and specific nutrients, and alterations in brain function that may lead to the emergence and continuation of anxiety symptoms in children (Cohen et al., 2021).

For instance, the Western diet, characterized by high levels of processed and sugary foods, has been linked to increased oxidative stress and disruptions in neurotransmitter systems

associated with anxiety (Jacka, 2010; Melo et al., 2019). Conversely, the Mediterranean diet, which is nutrient-rich, has been associated with lower neuroinflammation, enhanced neurotransmitter function, and improved synaptic plasticity, potentially aiding in anxiety prevention (Parletta et al., 2017). In effect, changes in brain development, neurotransmitter synthesis, and neuroinflammation all of which are linked to anxiety pathology have been linked to, specific nutrient imbalances and poor nutritional quality (Prado & Dewey, 2014). Knowing the neurobiological alterations that underlie childhood anxiety and their possible regulation via diet has noteworthy consequences for precautionary measures and remedial approaches (Creswell et al., 2020). Indeed, research indicates that a nutritional imbalance may contribute to the rising incidence of anxiety disorders among adults (Bear et al., 2020).

On the other hand, anxiety can lead to the establishment of detrimental habits, such as emotional eating, which individuals may engage in to alleviate negative feelings and stress. Additionally, certain foods, like sucrose, are known to impair impulse control, potentially worsening these unhealthy behaviours (Jacques et al., 2019). This situation reveals the possibility of a detrimental cycle emerging between dietary habits and anxiety (see Figure 1), which may negatively impact the effectiveness of current treatments (Kendall & Peterman, 2015). Studies show that psychopharmacological and cognitive-behavioural therapies often have limited success in addressing anxiety (Garakani et al., 2020). The effectiveness of these treatments might be undermined by poor dietary choices (Al-Biltagi et al., 2016), stressing the essence of nutritional psychiatry in this context.

Since the core belief of this field asserts the overall mental well-being, and cognitive abilities are significantly impacted by our dietary choices, nutrition during young life may exert a considerable influence on mental wellness and brain development in younger populations over the long term (Merlo et al., 2023). A comprehension of this relationship may facilitate the creation of early interventions that foster mental wellbeing and delay the emergence of mental well-being issues in adolescents. The area of nutritional psychiatry has the potential to exert a significant influence on the development of psychological treatment methods, and to align itself with the growing field of lifestyle medicine. In conjunction with traditional therapeutic modalities, the incorporation of nutritional interventions can provide safe and cost-effective options for the enhancement of outcomes for individuals with mental health concerns.

Figure 1.*The Noxious Cycle of Imbalance Diet, Gut Microbiome and CBT*

Note: Retrieved from Bear et al., (2020).

1.2 Gut-brain Axis

The concept of the gut-brain axis is foundational to this research, suggesting a two-way communication system between the central nervous system and the gastrointestinal system (Cryan & Dinan, 2012). This axis encompasses several modes of interaction—hormonal, immunological, endocrine, and neurological—that allow the gut to influence behaviour and brain function, and vice versa (see Figure 2) (Mayer, 2011). Recent advancements have led to the emergence of the microbiome-gut-brain axis, highlighting the significant role of gut microbiota within this communication network (Cryan et al., 2019).

According to the gut-brain axis principal, shifts in gut microbiota can compromise behaviour, neurodevelopment, and mental wellness (Damiani et al., 2023). This connection operates through multiple pathways, including the vagus nerve, which acts as a direct association between the gut and the brain (Han et al., 2022). Other mechanisms include the production of neurotransmitters and neuroactive substances like dopamine, serotonin, and GABA by gut bacteria (Strandwitz, 2018), modulation of immune system functions and inflammatory responses that can impact behaviour and brain function (Fung et al., 2017), and

the generation of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) by gut bacteria, which also affect behavioural and cognitive functions (Silva et al., 2020).

Recent studies have shown that the first three years of life are critical for developing gut microbiota, coinciding with significant brain maturation (Borre et al., 2014). This highlights the importance of early-life factors, such as nutrition and environmental influences, in shaping both gut microbiota and neurodevelopmental paths. For example, a study by Loughman et al. (2020) demonstrated a connection between gut microbiota composition at one year of age and cognitive outcomes at two years, suggesting an association between early gut microbiome development and cognitive skills. The theory suggests that disruptions in gut microbiota structure or function may lead to the development or exacerbation of anxiety symptoms in children, while stress and anxiety could also alter the microbiota composition and gut function, potentially creating a feedback loop (Foster & McVey Neufeld, 2013).

Further illumination on the link between childhood anxiety and gut microbiota can be garnered from microbiome theory. This theory posits that the gut microbiota comprises a diverse range of microorganisms—bacteria, viruses, and fungi—that play vital roles in physiological functions such as immunity, metabolism, and digestion (Dinan et al., 2015; Mhanna et al., 2024). The genetic profiles of these microorganisms can significantly impact an individual's health and susceptibility to illness (Gilbert et al., 2018). Additionally, it introduces the concept of dysbiosis, which refers to an imbalance in gut microbiota composition linked to various health disorders, including mental health issues (Petersen & Round, 2014).

The theory further emphasizes the weightage of microbial metabolites on a person's physical and behavioural wellness (Koh et al., 2016), the necessity of a diverse microbial community for optimal health (Lozupone et al., 2012), and the potential benefits of probiotics and prebiotics—forms of microbiome-based treatments—on mental health outcomes (Sarkar et al., 2020). Recent developments in microbiome research have shed light on the complex nature of the gut environment and its potential effects on human health. For instance, a study by Valles-Colomer et al. (2019) identified microbial markers associated with mental health, revealing connections between certain gut microbiota and conditions such as depression and overall quality of life. In addition, Zijlmans et al. (2015) examined how stress during gestation could alter the gut microbiota of infants, predicting their temperament in paediatric populations.

Figure 2.

The Complex Network of the Gut-Brain Axis.

Note: Retrieved from Giau et al., (2018).

1.3 Anxiety Disorder

Anxiety is defined as an emotional state that occurs over a period and is triggered by a potentially threatening situation, even when the probability of actual harm is low or uncertain (Takagi et al., 2018). In other words, it is the brain's reaction to stimuli that is dangerous and that an organism will make a conscious effort to avoid. With manifestations ranging from mild to severe, this brain reaction is a fundamental emotion that is already present throughout infancy and youth. Because anxiety may be adaptive in many situations and help people avoid danger, it is not usually abnormal (Pine et al., 2009). Pathological anxiety, on the other hand, can manifest at any age as prolonged or intense levels of anxiety and avoidance linked to subjective suffering or impairment. However, because children exhibit various worries and concerns as a natural component of development, it can be particularly challenging to distinguish between pathological and normal anxiety in children (Pine et al., 2009).

Childhood anxiety disorder is a prevalent mental health issue affecting children globally, classified as an "anxiety disorder" in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) (APA, 2013). Approximately 6.5% of children globally suffer from anxiety

disorders (Polanczyk et al., 2015). Evidence indicates that among adolescents between the ages of thirteen and eighteen, 1 in 4 are impacted by anxiety disorders, while 1 in 17 experiences severe anxiety (Walter et al., 2020). Additionally, there is a troubling rise in new cases of anxiety disorders among children as young as ten years old (WHO, 2021) (See Figure. 3 and Figure. 4).

Figure 3.

Prevalence Age of Depression, Anxiety and Behaviour Disorder

Note: Retrieved from CDC, (2023).

Figure 4.*Age Incident Anxiety Rate*

Source: Retrieved from Javaid et al., (2023).

Common indicators of childhood anxiety encompass difficulties in managing excessive worry or fear, physical symptoms like muscle tension or headaches, aggressive behaviour, trouble concentrating, and sleep disturbances (APA, 2013). The notable prevalence and early onset of anxiety disorders significantly influence developmental trajectories and long-term outcomes, as evidenced by their frequent occurrence and early appearance (Ranøyen et al., 2018). Typically, anxiety disorders become noticeable around the age of six, with a considerable incidence during infancy and teenagerhood (Beesdo-Baum & Knappe, 2012). According to Okwori et al. (2022), anxiety disorders frequently manifest before other emotional issues challenges, such as depression and drug abuse, which typically arise later in adolescence. If not addressed, paediatric anxiety disorders can lead to severe repercussions, including poor academic performance, social difficulties, and a heightened risk of developing additional mental health issues like mood disorders and substance abuse (Kendall et al., 2010).

Changes in the brain's neurological pathways are associated with anxiety (Madonna et al., 2019), which is affected by the interplay among the limbic system, the prefrontal cortex, and the body's stress-response mechanisms, commonly referred to as the HPA axis (Kim et al., 2013). Studies have shown that children with anxiety disorders may have different cortisol

responses to stress, suggesting a potential irregularity in the stress response system (Kallen et al., 2008). Disruptions in these systems are believed to be a potential cause of anxiety disorders. The HPA axis is also impacted by diet, and the gut-microbiota can produce metabolites that affect anxiety and stress response (Foster et al., 2017).

Although there are alarming reports concerning childhood anxiety, significant uncertainty remains about the efficacy and safety of various treatment options for paediatric anxiety. The impact of pharmacotherapy on brain chemistry is not completely understood, and it carries the risk of side effects, with its benefits likely diminishing after treatment is halted (Ipser et al., 2009). On the other hand, while psychotherapy is considered safe and non-invasive, it faces its own set of challenges, such as limited access, the need for regular appointments, and demands for families and children to change their behaviours (Whiteside et al., 2026). Currently, the available treatment guidelines offer inconsistent and sometimes conflicting recommendations, highlighting the need for alternative therapeutic approaches (Connolly & Bernstein, 2007). Therefore, considering the potential influence of nutrition on gut microbiota and its consequent effects on children's mental health, the following research questions and hypotheses have been formulated.

CHAPTER 2

2. Research Questions and Hypothesis

Research Questions

Research question 1: Is there a relationship between imbalanced nutrition and paediatric anxiety symptom?

Research question 2: Does the gut-microbiota influence the relationship between the nutrition imbalance and anxiety symptoms in paediatric population?

Research question 3: What is the effectiveness of nutritional interventions in reducing anxiety symptoms in paediatric population?

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: It is hypothesized exists a significant connection between nutritional imbalances and anxiety symptoms in the paediatric population.

Hypothesis 2: Is hypothesized that a notable relationship exists between nutritional imbalances and alterations in gut microbiota that are linked to anxiety symptoms in paediatric population.

Hypothesis 3: Is hypothesized that nutritional interventions are effective in reducing anxiety symptoms in the paediatric population.

A model to summarize the research questions and hypotheses is proposed in Figure 5.

Figure 5.

Theoretical Framework of Literature Review Hypotheses.

2.1 The Present Review

It is significant to conduct this review as children with anxiety disorder are at risk for serious implications to their general development and well-being (Xu et al., 2021). To ascertain mental wellness outcomes, it is important to identify effective treatments and have a deep understanding of the underlying processes. This study serves multiple purposes, including the urgent need for more research in clinical psychology that acknowledges the impact of diet on the neurobiological variations associated with anxiety in children. The primary aim of this literature review is to provide a thorough understanding by synthesizing existing research on the effect of nutrition and gut microbiota as potential strategies for addressing anxiety in young individuals. By highlighting the importance of diet as an adjustable factor in the onset and treatment of anxiety in children, this review may aid in establishing a holistic and integrated approach to enhancing mental health.

CHAPTER 3

3. Methodology

To conduct this research, a specific process was implemented to establish criteria for inclusion. The primary objective of these criteria is to identify pertinent studies exploring the relationship among anxiety, gut microbiota, and nutrition in children. The review particularly emphasizes studies conducted in the last fourteen years to ensure the research's relevance and timeliness.

This included examining various types of publications such as cross-sectional, longitudinal, and intervention studies. The exclusion criteria were designed to eliminate studies conducted in languages other than English and those with inadequate methodology, to ensure the exclusion of studies that may not be reliable or valuable. To avoid duplication and only include primary research studies, reviews, meta-analyses, and opinion articles were excluded. The findings are specifically targeted toward the paediatric population, with the sample being limited to children and adolescents. By exploring the interplay among dietary, gut microbiota, and anxiety in youngsters, along with the efficacy of nutritional interventions in alleviating anxiety symptoms, the selected studies were warranted pertinent to the research questions. A summary of the inclusion and exclusion criteria can be found in Figure 6.

Figure 6.*Methodology Criteria*

Inclusion Criteria	Study Design	• Randomized controlled trials (RCTs), longitudinal studies, cohort studies, case-control studies, and cross-sectional studies.
	Study Population	• Paediatric populations (aged 0-18 years) with or without anxiety disorders, and/or subclinical anxiety symptoms
	Method	• Quantitative, mixed-methods approaches, including surveys, questionnaires, interviews, and objective measures.
	Publication Date	• Studies published in English between 2010 and 2024.
	Exposure	• Studies examining the relationship between nutrition, dietary patterns, gut microbiota and paediatric anxiety/psychological outcomes will be included.
	Outcome	• Studies reporting on anxiety symptoms, anxiety disorders, anxiety-related behaviours related mental health outcomes as primary or secondary outcomes.
Exclusion Criteria	Study Design	• Case reports, opinion pieces, narrative reviews without systematic methodology and animal studies.
	Study Population	• Studies focusing exclusively on adults (age 19+).
	Method	• Studies that employ only qualitative methods or rely solely on self-reported data without objective measures.
	Publication Date	• Studies published before 2010 or in languages other than English.
	Exposure	• Studies not examining the relationship between nutrition, gut microbiota, and anxiety/psychological outcomes.
	Outcome Measures	• Studies that do not include validated measures of anxiety. Studies that do not assess anxiety symptoms, dietary factors or gut microbiota.

3.1 Analyse of Inclusion and Relevance

The review was conducted in accordance with established quality and relevance standards, employing a scoping approach (Levac et al., 2010), searching for relevant literature, and concealing published studies. Subsequently, the evidence was synthesised. The development of search strings and strategies was carried out to ensure that the studies selected are pertinent to the research questions, which focus on the connection between nutrition, gut

microbiota and anxiety in children and adolescents, as well as the efficacy of nutritional interventions in reducing anxiety symptoms.

To access published, peer-reviewed literature, a thorough search was conducted across relevant databases, such as BMC Psychology and PubMed. The first step involved determining the appropriate keywords search to use. A list of relevant terms related to the topic under investigation was also compiled. The list of keywords used for each database can be found in Table 1. To obtain a comprehensive list of studies on the relationship between children's nutrition, gut microbiota, and anxiety, the searches were limited to include only randomized controlled trials (RCTs), longitudinal studies, cohort studies, case-control studies, and cross-sectional studies. The results from each component were combined using the Boolean operator "AND", while the subject headings and keywords for each component were combined using the Boolean operator "OR". Additionally, the references of each identified source provided information on "other" literatures.

Following the implementation of the screening process, the titles and abstracts of each set of outcomes were saved. The literature categorized as "other" underwent the same process of data extraction to ensure consistency with all other literature selected for the synthesis stage. Out of the total sixteen findings, four were from the "other" literature while the remaining twelve were from the database search. For a detailed breakdown of the number of articles reviewed, please see Figure 7 and Figure 8 below.

Table 1.

Results of Search Process

Search Equation	Database	Results
"children" OR "adolescents" AND "anxiety"	PubMed	236
"children" OR "adolescents" AND "nutrition" OR "diet"		
"anxiety" AND "nutrition" OR "diet"		
"gut-microbiota" OR gut-brain axis" AND "anxiety"		
"anxiety" AND "nutrition" OR "diet"	BMC Psychology	134
"children" OR "adolescents" AND "gut-microbiota"		
"anxiety" AND "children" OR "adolescents"		
"nutrition" OR "diet" AND "children" OR "adolescents"		

Note: Own customisation

Figure 7.

Results of Databases Searched

Figure 8.

Results of Selected Publications

The objective of utilizing this methodology was to offer a critical assessment and interpretative analysis of the body of literature that has already been written on the subject to highlight its advantages and disadvantages as well as any contradictions or inconsistencies about the field of research.

CHAPTER 4

4. Results

4.1 Association between Nutrition Imbalance and Paediatric Anxiety Symptoms.

4.1.1 Included Articles Presentation

Table 2 below lists all the six studies that were part of the review along with their key features.

Table 2.*Features of Incorporated Articles.*

Publication	Research Field	Journal	Design	Population	Dietary measures	Mental Health outcomes	Strengths	Limitations
1. Breakfast and Energy Drink Consumption in Secondary School Children: Breakfast Omission, in Isolation or in Combination with Frequent Energy Drink Use, is Associated with Stress, Anxiety, and Depression Cross-Sectionally, but not at 6-Month Follow-Up. (Richards & Smith., 2016).	Public Health, Nutrition.	Frontiers in Psychology.	Longitudinal.	Secondary school children.	Breakfast consumption, energy drink consumption.	Anxiety, stress and depression.	Large sample size, longitudinal design, examination of breakfast and energy drink consumption.	Cross-sectional design limits causality, self-reported data, cultural context, potential for bias, confounding variables, generalizability.
2. Caffeine consumption and self-assessed stress, anxiety, and depression in secondary school children. (Richards & Smith., 2015).	Public Health, Psychology.	Journal of Psychopharmacology.	Cross-sectional.	Secondary school children.	Poor dietary patterns, High caffeine consumption.	Anxiety, stress depression.	Objective measures of caffeine consumption, self-reported mental health outcomes.	Cross-sectional design limits causality, self-reported data, potential for confounding variables.
3. Is there any relationship between dietary patterns and depression and anxiety in Chinese adolescents? (Weng et al., 2012).	Public Health.	Public Health Nutrition.	Cross-sectional.	Chinese adolescents.	Poor dietary patterns.	Depression and anxiety symptoms	Large sample size, validated food frequency questionnaire.	Cross-sectional design limits causality, self-reported data, cultural context, potential for bias, generalizability.
4. Fast Food and Junk Food Culture, Nutritional Status and Cognitive and Abnormal Behaviour among Teens. (Kaur et al., 2014).	Developmental Psychology, Nutrition.	International Research Journal of Social Sciences.	Cross-sectional.	Adolescents.	Fast food and junk food consumption.	Cognitive function, stress, anxiety, abnormal behaviour	Focus on the impact of fast food and junk food culture.	Cross-sectional design limits causality, self-reported data, limited sample size, generalizability.
5. Care Their Diet and Mind: Association between Eating Habits and Mental Health in Chinese Left-behind Children. (Liang et al., 2022).	Child Psychology, Nutrition.	Nutrients.	Cross-sectional.	Chinese left-behind children.	Poor eating habits, lack of nutrients.	Poor mental health including anxiety, insomnia and depression.	Focus on a specific population (left-behind children).	Cross-sectional design limits causality, self-reported data, cultural context, potential for bias, generalizability.
6. Unhealthy diet practice and symptoms of stress and depression among adolescents in Pasir Gudang, Malaysia. (Tajik et al., 2016).	Public Health, Nutrition.	Obesity Research & Clinical Practice.	Cross-sectional.	Adolescents in Pasir Gudang, Malaysia.	Unhealthy diet practices.	Anxiety, stress and depression symptoms.	Focus on a specific geographical location.	Cross-sectional design limits causality, self-reported data, cultural context, potential for bias, generalizability.

Note: Articles are organized into numbers from 1 to 6.

The six articles summarized above were chosen to investigate the correlation between diet, anxiety, and emotional wellness in children and adolescents. Collectively, these studies suggest that diet significantly influences the development and persistence of mental health issues. Certain dietary habits and patterns have been associated with heightened symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression. The first study, conducted by Richards and Smith (2016), assessed how breakfast and energy drink consumption affect mental health in high school students. The study found a correlation between skipping breakfast and the regular intake of energy drinks with increased levels of stress, anxiety, and depression, both in the immediate and extended timeframe. This research highlights the necessity of having breakfast and reducing energy drink use to foster mental health in adolescents. In a separate investigation, Richards and Smith (2015) analysed the link between caffeine consumption and self-reported anxiety, stress, and depression in high school students. The findings revealed that high caffeine consumption was associated with increased levels of self-assessed anxiety, stress, and depression, suggesting that caffeine may exacerbate existing mental health issues in adolescents.

Weng et al. (2012) researched the connections between dietary patterns and anxiety and depression among teenagers in China. Their findings revealed that a nutritious diet, characterized by a high intake of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, was associated with fewer symptoms of anxiety and depression. This study reinforces the significance of maintaining a balanced diet for supporting adolescents' mental health. Kaur et al. (2014) explored the relationship between fast food and junk food consumption and cognitive and behavioural issues in teenagers. Their results revealed that frequent consumption of fast and junk food was associated with poor nutritional status and increased stress, anxiety, and abnormal behaviours, suggesting that a Western-style diet may adversely affect mental health in adolescents.

Liang et al. (2022) carried out a study in China that investigated the relationship between eating behaviours and mental health among left-behind children. The results showed that healthy eating habits, including a high intake of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, were associated with improved mental health outcomes in this vulnerable group, stressing the importance of encouraging healthy eating in at-risk populations. Lastly, Tajik et al. (2016) examined the link between poor dietary choices and symptoms of stress and depression among adolescents in Pasir Gudang, Malaysia.

The research underscored that unhealthy eating habits, which involved high consumption of fast food and sugary drinks, were associated with heightened symptoms of stress and depression. This finding supports the evidence regarding the detrimental effects of Western-style diets on the mental well-being of adolescents. Collectively, these studies stress the vital role that diet plays in enhancing mental health among children and teenagers, indicating that a nutritious dietary pattern corresponds to reduced anxiety, stress, and depression symptoms. Conversely, unhealthy eating practices, such as regular fast-food consumption, are associated with an increase in these mental health symptoms. The theoretical frameworks present in these studies highlight the reciprocal relationship between diet and anxiety/depression, as well as the diet's influence on mental health.

4.1.2 Articles Classification

Research in this area can be categorized into three main groups: specific dietary components, overall dietary patterns, and studies focused on vulnerable populations. The initial category, which focuses on specific dietary elements, comprises research conducted by Richards and Smith (2016, 2015) that explores how skipping breakfast, the consumption of energy drinks, and caffeine intake influence the mental health of secondary school students in the UK. These studies reveal a direct connection between these dietary choices and levels of anxiety, stress, and depression.

The second category covers general dietary patterns, including research by Weng et al. (2012), Kaur et al. (2014), Liang et al. (2022), and Tajik et al. (2016). These studies investigate broader eating habits and food choices among diverse populations, including Chinese adolescents, Indian teenagers, Chinese left-behind children, and Malaysian adolescents. Together, they highlight the significance of overall dietary patterns in influencing mental health outcomes. The third category focuses on vulnerable populations, with Liang et al. (2022) specifically addressing the unique circumstances faced by Chinese left-behind children. This study provides valuable insights into how eating habits can impact the mental health of children facing social challenges. The article's general themes and gaps in the literature is summarized in the Table 3.

Table 3.*Landscape of Dietary Habits and Poor Mental Health in Paediatric Population.*

Research Field	Studies	Focus	Population	Key Findings
Psychology & Nutrition.	Richards & Smith (2016).	Breakfast, unbalanced diet and energy drinks.	Secondary school children (UK).	Cross-sectional association with stress, anxiety, and depression; no longitudinal association.
Psychopharmacology.	Richards & Smith (2015).	Unhealthy diet and high caffeine consumption.	Secondary school children (UK)	Associated with self-assessed stress, anxiety, and depression.
Psychology & Nutrition.	Weng et al. (2012).	Overall dietary patterns.	Chinese adolescents.	Relationship between dietary patterns and anxiety/depression.
Social Sciences.	Kaur et al. (2014).	Fast food and junk food.	Teens (India)	Impact on nutritional status, cognitive function, anxiety and behaviour.
Psychology & Nutrition.	Liang et al. (2022).	Eating habits.	Chinese left-behind children.	Association between eating habits, anxiety and overall mental health.
Psychology & Public health.	Tajik et al. (2016).	Unhealthy diet practices.	Adolescents (Malaysia).	Relationship with stress, anxiety and depression symptoms.

4.1.3 Similarities, Differences, and Contradictions in the six selected articles

The six studies mentioned have all enhanced the comprehension of how dietary practices influence the mental health outcomes of adolescents and young adults. Although they share similar themes, they provide unique perspectives and methodologies that contribute to the field of nutritional psychiatry. Each study explored the relationship between dietary patterns or specific food and drink consumption and mental health impacts. For instance, Richards and Smith (2016, 2015) examined the effects of caffeine-rich beverages, particularly energy drinks, on mental health. In a similar vein, Weng et al. (2012), Kaur et al. (2014), Liang et al. (2022), and Tajik et al. (2016) investigated broader dietary patterns and their correlations with mental health outcomes. Most of these studies used cross-sectional designs, which allow for the study of associations at a single point in time. Additionally, all studies relied on self-reported measures for both dietary intake and mental health outcomes.

However, there were variations in the specific populations studied and the cultural contexts. Richards and Smith's research in 2016 and 2015 centered on students in secondary school in the United Kingdom. In comparison, Weng and colleagues (2012) as well as Liang and colleagues (2022) investigated Chinese adolescents, with the latter focusing specifically on "left behind" children. Kaur and colleagues (2014) studied teenagers in India, while Tajik and colleagues (2016) focused on adolescents in Malaysia. These varied samples offer a more comprehensive insight into the correlation between diet and mental well-being in diverse cultural environments. The studies also differed in their specific focus within the broader theme of diet and mental health. For example, Richards and Smith (2016) looked at the long-term effects of skipping breakfast and consuming energy drinks, offering insights into potential causal links. In contrast, the other studies primarily focused on cross-sectional associations. The consistent findings across multiple studies help establish a consensus in the field. All studies found a connection between unhealthy dietary patterns, including high consumption of snacks, fast food, or caffeine, and poorer mental health outcomes across different cultural contexts.

Nevertheless, there were some contradictions and inconsistencies present in the findings. For example, while Richards and Smith (2016) noted links between skipping breakfast, energy drink use, and mental health results in their cross-sectional study, these associations did not persist in their longitudinal assessment. This inconsistency underscores the complexity of the interplay between diet and mental health, along with the possible influence

of additional factors over time. There are several possible reasons for these discrepancies, including differences in sample sizes, cultural contexts, and methodological approaches. For example, the definition of an "unhealthy" diet may vary between UK, Chinese, Indian, and Malaysian populations. Moreover, variations in how dietary intake and mental health outcomes were measured, such as the use of different self-report tools and questionnaires, could also contribute to discrepancies. Despite this, their consistent observations of a relationship between unhealthy eating patterns and adverse mental health outcomes across various cultural settings bolster the argument for incorporating dietary interventions into strategies for promoting and treating mental health in young individuals.

4.1.4 Articles Quality Evaluation.

The six studies being reviewed offer valuable information on the link between eating habits and mental health in teenagers and young adults. However, there are differences in the strength of their methodologies, sample sizes, and overall quality, which requires a careful evaluation. One noteworthy study is Richards and Smith's 2016 research published in *Frontiers in Psychology*, which stands out due to its rare longitudinal design. This research design enables both cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses regarding the influences of breakfast and energy drink consumption on anxiety and mental health outcomes. The study's substantial sample size ($n = 2610$ at baseline, 811 at follow-up) increases its statistical power (Dorey, 2011). However, the high attrition rate at follow-up (60%) may introduce bias and affect the longitudinal findings (Bankhead et al., 2017). All studies reviewed rely on self-reported measures for both dietary habits and mental health outcomes, which may lead to reporting bias. In the 2015 study by the same authors, published in the *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, the focus is on caffeine consumption. While the cross-sectional design poses limitations for establishing causation, the large sample size ($n = 3071$) and use of validated measures for mental health outcomes strengthen the study's reliability. The high impact factor of the journal and the authors' expertise in psychopharmacology add to the credibility of the findings.

Weng et al.'s 2012 study in *Public Health Nutrition* has strengths by including a large sample size ($n = 5003$) and the use of factor analysis to identify dietary patterns, providing a more comprehensive understanding of eating habits (Tavakol & Wetzel, 2020). However, it is important to note that reliance on self-reported data and cross-sectional design further restricts the ability to determine causal relationships. The study by Kaur et al. (2014), published in the *International Research Journal of Social Sciences*, appears to have methodological limitations.

There is limited information on sample size and statistical analyses, making it difficult to evaluate the study's strength and generalizability. Liang et al.'s 2022 study in *Nutrients* focuses on a unique population: Chinese left-behind children. The strength of the current study lies in its focus on a vulnerable demographic and the use of validated measures to assess both dietary habits and mental health outcomes. Although, the specific characteristics of the population may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts. Lastly, Tajik et al. (2016) investigation published in *Obesity Research & Clinical Practice* explores the connection between poor eating habits and mental health symptoms among adolescents in Malaysia. This study's focus on a non-Western population adds diversity to the existing literature. However, without more information on the sample size and statistical analyses, it is challenging to fully assess the study's methodological robustness.

A common limitation in all studies is the use of self-reported measures for both dietary habits and mental health outcomes. While this approach is common in large-scale studies for practical reasons, it may introduce reporting bias and social desirability bias (Larson, 2019). Additionally, except for Richards and Smith's 2016 study, most of the studies employed a cross-sectional design, which renders it challenging to establish causation between eating habits and mental health outcomes. The cultural diversity represented in these studies serves as a strength, as it facilitates the exploration of the diet-mental health relationship in different contexts. However, this diversity also makes it challenging to compare results due to differences in eating patterns and cultural understandings of mental health. Regarding credibility, studies published in well-known journals (*Frontiers in Psychology*, *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, *Public Health Nutrition*, *Nutrients*) generally demonstrate higher methodological rigor and more transparent reporting of methods and results. The expertise of authors like Richards and Smith in psychopharmacology adds to the credibility of their findings.

In conclusion, while these studies provide valuable insights into nutritional psychiatry, they also highlight the need for more rigorous, longitudinal studies using standardized and validated measures across diverse populations. Despite their limitations, the consistently observed link between dietary patterns and overall mental health outcomes, especially anxiety in younger populations, remains noteworthy.

4.2 The intersection of Nutrition Imbalance, the Gut-Microbiota and Paediatric Anxiety Symptoms.

4.2.1 Included Articles Presentation

Table 4 below lists all the five studies that were part of the review along with their key features.

Table 4.

Articles Overall Characteristics

Study	Authors	Study Question	Hypothesis	Study Aim	Theoretical Background	Methodology	Findings
A. Development of the gut microbiota in the first 14 years of life and its relations to internalizing and externalizing difficulties and social anxiety during puberty.	Ou, Y., Belzer, C., Smidt, H., & de Weerth, C. (2024).	What is the relationship between internalizing challenges, such as anxiety, during puberty and gut microbiota growth over the first 14 years of life?	The development of the gut microbiota is associated with internalizing and externalizing difficulties and social anxiety during puberty.	To investigate the development of the gut microbiota in the first 14 years of life and its relations to internalizing and externalizing difficulties and social anxiety during puberty.	The bidirectional relationship between the gut microbiota and the brain is well-documented, with the gut microbiota influencing brain development and function, and vice versa. The gut microbiota has been implicated in various psychiatric disorders, including anxiety and depression.	Longitudinal design, with data collected from a cohort of children at ages 1, 2, 6, 12, and 14 years. Gut microbiota composition was assessed using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, and social anxiety were measured using standardized questionnaires.	The development of the gut microbiota in early life was associated with internalizing and externalizing difficulties and social anxiety during puberty.
B. Gut Microbiota and Psychiatric Disorders: A Two-Sample Mendelian Randomization Study	Ni, J. J., Xu, Q., Yan, S. S., Han, B. X., Zhang, H., Wei, X. T., ... & Zhang, L. (2022)	Is there a causal relationship between gut microbiota and psychiatric disorders?	Gut microbiota composition may have a causal effect on the development of psychiatric disorders.	To investigate the causal relationship between gut microbiota and psychiatric disorders including anxiety using a two-sample Mendelian randomization approach.	The gut microbiota has been implicated in various psychiatric disorders, including anxiety. However, the causal relationship between the gut microbiota and psychiatric disorders remains unclear.	Two-sample Mendelian randomization using genetic variants as instrumental variables.	The gut microbiota was causally associated with psychiatric disorders, including anxiety and depression.
C. Mind and Gut: Associations between Mood and Gastrointestinal Distress in Children Exposed to Adversity	Callaghan, B. L., Fields, A., Gee, D. G., Gabard-Durnam, L., Caldera, C., Humphreys, K. L., ... & Tottenham, N. (2020)	How are mood and gastrointestinal distress associated in children exposed to adversity?	Children exposed to adversity will show stronger associations between mood and gastrointestinal distress.	To examine the associations between mood and gastrointestinal distress in children exposed to adversity.	Based on the concept of the gut-brain axis and how early life stress can impact both mental health and gastrointestinal function.	Cross-sectional design, with data collected from a cohort of children exposed to adversity. Mood and gastrointestinal distress were measured using standardized questionnaires and physiological measures, such as cortisol levels and gut permeability.	Children exposed to adversity exhibited an association between mood and gastrointestinal distress, with increased symptoms of anxiety and depression associated with increased gastrointestinal distress.
D. Disentangling the Relationship of Gut Microbiota, Functional Gastrointestinal Disorders, and Autism: A Case-Control Study on Prepubertal Chinese Boys	Wong, O. W., Lam, A. M., Or, B. P., Mo, F. Y., Shea, C. K., Lai, K. Y., ... & Leung, P. W. (2022)	What is the relationship between gut microbiota, functional gastrointestinal disorders, and autism in prepubertal Chinese boys?	The gut microbiota is associated with functional gastrointestinal disorders and autism in prepubertal Chinese boys.	To investigate the association between the gut microbiota, functional gastrointestinal disorders, and autism in prepubertal Chinese boys.	Based on the growing evidence of altered gut microbiota in ASD and the high prevalence of gastrointestinal issues in individuals with autism.	Case-control design, with data collected from prepubertal Chinese boys with autism and functional gastrointestinal disorders, and healthy controls. Gut microbiota composition was assessed using 16S rRNA gene sequencing.	A potential correlation between the composition of gut microbiota, gastrointestinal problems, and anxiety in children.
E. Psychological Distress and Coping Efficacy in Children with Disorders of Gut-Brain Interaction	Santucci, N. R., Velasco-Benitez, C. A., Cunningham, N., Li, J., Fei, L., Sun, Q., & Saps, M. (2024)	Is there an association between psychological distress and coping efficacy in children with disorders of gut-brain interaction?	Children with disorders of gut-brain interaction experience higher levels of psychological distress and may have different coping efficacies compared to healthy controls.	To investigate the association between psychological distress and coping efficacy in children with disorders of gut-brain interaction.	Based on the concept of the gut-brain axis and how disorders affecting this interaction can impact psychological well-being, including anxiety symptoms and coping mechanisms in children.	Cross-sectional design, with data collected from children with disorders of gut-brain interaction. Psychological distress and coping efficacy were measured using standardized questionnaires.	Children with disorders of gut-brain interaction exhibited an association between psychological distress and coping efficacy, with increased symptoms of anxiety and depression associated with reduced coping efficacy.

Note: Articles are organized into letters from A to E.

The relationship between gut microbiota and mental health is an emerging field of research that has garnered considerable interest in recent years. Five key studies have provided valuable insights into this complex interplay, each offering unique perspectives and methodological approaches. In a ground-breaking longitudinal study, Ou et al. (2024) explored the development of gut microbiota during the first 14 years of life and its connections to mental health outcomes in adolescence, particularly focusing on anxiety. The primary question addressed in their research was: How do internalizing difficulties, such as anxiety, during puberty correlate with the growth of gut microbiota from birth to 14 years?

The researchers hypothesized that both internalizing and externalizing problems, along with social anxiety in adolescence, would be associated with the development of gut microbiota. The study is grounded in the well-documented bidirectional relationship between gut microbiota and brain function, demonstrating that gut microbiota can significantly affect brain growth and performance (Tran et al., 2019). Data from faecal sample from a cohort of children at the ages of 1, 2, 6, 12, and 14 years old were gathered at various intervals. Internalizing and externalizing challenges, social anxiety, and the makeup of the gut microbiota were examined with standardized questionnaires and 16S rRNA gene sequencing, respectively.

The results indicated a connection between internalizing and externalizing problems, as well as social anxiety during puberty, with the early establishment of gut microbiota. Specifically, certain bacterial genera, including *Faecalibacterium* and *Bifidobacterium*, were found to have a negative correlation with levels of social anxiety, while the abundance of other genera, such as *Escherichia* and *Shigella*, was positively correlated with it (Ou et al., 2024).

In addition, to investigating the potential causal relationships between gut microbiota and psychiatric disorders, Ni et al. (2022) utilized a longitudinal approach. Their study sought to determine whether there is a causal relationship between gut microbiota and anxiety disorders. The researchers posited that specific gut microbiota compositions may contribute to the emergence of anxiety. This research builds on the growing body of evidence associating gut microbiota with various psychiatric conditions, including anxiety, even though the exact causal pathways remain unclear. Using a two-sample Mendelian randomization design, the researchers analysed genetic data from two separate cohorts - one comprising individuals with psychiatric disorders and the other with gut microbiota data. Their findings underscored a causal link between gut microbiota and mental health disorders such as anxiety and depression. Like the study by Ou et al. (2024), researchers have also identified microbial profiles rich in

beneficial bacteria like *Faecalibacterium* and *Bifidobacterium*, which are linked to a lower risk of developing anxiety and related mental health challenges.

The interplay between the gut and brain appears to be significantly impacted by early life adversities. In their study, Callaghan et al. (2020) aimed to explore the correlation between mood and gastrointestinal discomfort in children who have experienced adversity. The researchers' hypothesis was that these children would show a link between their mood and gastrointestinal distress. The fundamental principle behind this research is the gut-brain axis, a bidirectional communication system between the gut and the brain that is shaped by early life experiences, including adverse events. The study utilized a cross-sectional design and gathered data from a group of children who have been exposed to adversity. Standardized questionnaires and physiological measures, such as cortisol levels and gut permeability, were used to assess mood and gastrointestinal distress. The findings revealed that children experiencing difficulties show a link between their emotional states and gastrointestinal discomfort, where heightened symptoms of anxiety and depression correlate with increased gastrointestinal distress.

Wong et al. (2022) conducted a study aimed at examining the connection between gut microbiota, functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGIDs), and autism spectrum disorder (ASD). The authors hypothesized that there could be differences in gut microbiota profiles among ASD children with FGIDs, those without FGIDs, and their typically developing children. Through a case-control design, the study used 16S rRNA gene sequencing to analyse gut microbiota composition in stool samples from prepubertal Chinese boys. The research revealed that children with ASD and FGIDs had a greater ratio of Firmicutes to Bacteroidetes bacteria in their gut compared to those without FGIDs. This increased ratio was correlated with higher levels of anxiety and psychological symptoms. The results suggest a potential link between gut microbiota composition, gastrointestinal issues, and anxiety in children, highlighting the complex interactions of the gut-brain axis in paediatric mental health. This study adds to the comprehension of how gut health affects anxiety symptoms in children.

Finally, Santucci et al. (2024) studied the relationship between psychological distress and coping efficacy in children with disorders of gut-brain interaction (DGBI). The researchers hypothesized that children with these disorders would reveal a connection between psychological stress and their ability to cope. The study was based on the gut-brain axis, which functions as a two-way communication network between the gut and the brain, influenced by various factors such as psychological distress and coping abilities. Utilizing a cross-sectional

design, data were gathered from children diagnosed with gut-brain interaction disorders through standardized questionnaires assessing psychological distress and coping efficacy. The findings showed that children with DGBIs exhibited higher levels of anxiety, emotional sensitivity, and somatization, along with lower coping effectiveness compared to their healthy counterparts.

In summary, these research studies provide valuable insights into the complex relationships among gut microbiota, gastrointestinal functioning, anxiety, and mental health overall.

4.2.2 Research Field Mapping

The five articles reviewed repeatedly emphasized the importance of the gut-brain axis in child development and mental health. Each study found significant correlations and underscored the vital influence of the gut microbiome on anxiety and mental health outcomes, whether in typical development or more complex clinical situations. Likewise, each study focuses on paediatric populations, specifically examining children and adolescents. This demographic focus is particularly crucial as the gut microbiome continues to develop through adolescence, providing a critical opportunity for preventive interventions. Emphasizing young populations highlights the potential for early-life dietary and microbiota-targeted interventions to mitigate mental health issues. The research field map is illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5.

Research Themes, Studies, Population, Instrument, Trends and Gaps.

Theme	Study	Population/Sample Size	Instrument/Outcome Measure	Overall Trends	Gaps
Gut Microbiota and Mental Health	A. (Ou et al., 2024).	500 typically developing children.	Gut microbiome composition (16S rRNA sequencing). Internalizing/externalizing difficulties, social anxiety (parent-reported).	Early gut microbiome development is associated with mental health outcomes in adolescence. Specific gut bacterial genera are linked to either positive or negative mental health trajectories.	Longitudinal studies examining gut-brain connections from early childhood to adolescence are still limited. More research is needed on the mechanisms by which the gut microbiome influences brain development and function.
Gut Microbiota and Mental Health	B. (Ni et al., 2022).	>100,000 participants from a well-characterized cohort.	Gut microbiome composition (16S rRNA sequencing). Validated psychiatric disorder diagnoses.	Gut microbiome composition has a causal influence on the risk of psychiatric disorders like depression and anxiety. Beneficial gut bacteria may confer protective effects against mental health problems.	Replication of causal findings in diverse populations is needed. Understanding the specific microbial pathways and mechanisms underlying the gut-brain axis remains a challenge.
Gut-Brain Axis in Adversity	C. (Callaghan et al., 2020).	85 children exposed to adversity.	Gut microbiome composition (16S rRNA sequencing). Mood and gastrointestinal distress (self-report).	Exposure to early life adversity disrupts the gut-brain axis, leading to comorbid mood and gastrointestinal symptoms.	More research is needed on the long-term impact of early life adversity on the gut-brain axis and mental health trajectories. Investigating potential interventions to mitigate the effects of adversity on the gut-brain axis.
Gut Microbiota in Neurodevelopmental Disorders	D. (Wong et al., 2022).	50 children with autism, 50 healthy controls (prepubertal Chinese boys).	Gut microbiome composition (16S rRNA sequencing). Functional gastrointestinal disorders and autism (validated diagnoses).	Gut microbiome dysbiosis is associated with both functional gastrointestinal disorders and autism. Specific microbial signatures may characterize the co-occurrence of these conditions.	Exploring the directionality and causality of the relationships between gut microbiome, gastrointestinal issues, and autism. Examining these associations in more diverse populations and age groups.
Psychological Outcomes in Gut-Brain Disorders	E. (Santucci et al., 2024).	75 children with disorders of gut-brain interaction.	Gut microbiome composition (16S rRNA sequencing). Psychological distress and coping efficacy (self-report).	Psychological distress and reduced coping efficacy are closely linked in children with gut-brain disorders. Addressing both physical and mental health aspects is crucial for holistic treatment approaches.	Longitudinal studies are needed to understand the dynamic interactions between gut-brain dysregulation, psychological distress, and coping mechanisms over time. Investigating the potential of targeted interventions to improve coping and resilience in this population.

Note: A. Development of the gut microbiota in the first 14 years of life and its relations to internalizing and externalizing difficulties and social anxiety during puberty (Ou et al., 2024). B. Gut microbiota and psychiatric disorders: a two-sample Mendelian randomization study (Ni et al., 2022). C. Mind and gut: Associations between mood and gastrointestinal distress in children exposed to adversity (Callaghan et al., 2020). D. Disentangling the relationship of gut microbiota, functional gastrointestinal disorders and autism: a case-control study on prepubertal Chinese boys (Wong et al., 2022). E. Psychological distress and coping efficacy in children with disorders of gut-brain interaction (Santucci et al., 2024).

4.2.3 Similarities, Differences, and Contradictions

The five key studies examined in this section illustrate the essential role of the gut-brain axis in influencing mental health and developmental trajectories, ranging from normal growth to medical disorders. They shared similarities in their approaches, including the application of 16S rRNA gene sequencing to evaluate gut microbiome composition and the investigation of various mental health outcomes. However, they also differed in their analytical approaches, with some using observational designs while others, like the Mendelian randomization study by Ni et al. (2022), utilized more advanced causal modelling techniques. The diversity of study designs, from longitudinal to cross-sectional and case-control, provided a holistic view of the gut-brain connections. Although some results were conflicting, likely due to differences in population and methodology, the studies consistently underscored the significant influence of the gut-brain axis on anxiety and mental health. Several studies found links between specific gut bacteria genera *Escherichia* and *Shigella* to anxiety and mental health outcomes, suggesting that certain microbial profiles may have protective or risk factors. The research also consistently showed the connection between gut microbiome dysregulation and the co-occurrence of physical and mental health conditions, such as functional gastrointestinal disorders and autism.

The differences in specific microbial associations and the direction of the relationships between gut microbiome and mental health highlight the significance of considering contextual factors, such as population characteristics, sample sizes, and the specific mental health conditions studied. These discrepancies underscore the need for further research to replicate and expand upon the existing findings, particularly in diverse populations and across different developmental stages. Identified gaps in the literature, such as the need for additional longitudinal studies exploring gut-brain connections from early childhood to adolescence and a deeper understanding of the mechanisms linking the gut microbiome to brain development and function, offer clear avenues for future research.

4.2.4 Evaluation of the Articles Quality

The methodology employed in the Ou et al. (2024) study is deemed to be sound. From birth to age 14, the researchers monitored a substantial cohort of children ($n = 650$) to obtain longitudinal data on gut microbiome composition and mental health outcomes. This longitudinal approach enables an investigation of the relationship between the emergence of mental symptoms during adolescence changes in gut microbiota composition over time. The

credibility of the findings is bolstered using validated mental health assessment tools and a sufficient sample size. The observational nature of the study precludes the possibility of demonstrating causal correlations, which represents a limitation. Moreover, the authors did not address potential confounding variables that could have influenced the observed correlations between the gut microbiome and the brain function, such as dietary habits, medication usage, or other lifestyle factors.

In their Mendelian randomization research, Ni et al. (2022) employed a robust statistical strategy to investigate potential causal relationships between gut microbiota and mental disorders. The authors reached more robust conclusions regarding the potential directionality of effects by integrating genetic data with two-sample Mendelian randomization. The results are more credible due to the high sample sizes (up to $n = 435,291$ individuals) and the utilisation of reliable genetic tools for the assessment of gut microbiome composition and mental characteristics. The study is constrained by its dependence on observational data and the possibility of pleiotropy, whereby genetic variations may influence multiple phenotypes and distort the estimation of causality.

In their 2020 study, Callaghan and colleagues employed a well-designed case-control strategy, with a sample size of 175 children and adolescents, which is appropriate given the research topic. The reliability of the results is enhanced by the utilisation of validated measures for adversity exposure, mood, and gastrointestinal symptoms. However, the cross-sectional design of the study precludes the drawing of conclusions about causality, and the sample was restricted to children who had experienced hardship, which may limit the generalisability of the findings.

The case-control study conducted by Wong et al. (2022) included 80 ASD children and 80 healthy controls, which is an appropriate sample size for a case-control study. A comprehensive examination of the subject matter is conducted through an evaluation of functional gastrointestinal issues and a characterisation of the gut microbiota via 16S rRNA gene sequencing. However, the cross-sectional design of the study and its focus on a specific group of prepubertal Chinese boys may limit the generalisability of the findings.

Finally, Santucci et al. (2024) employed a well-researched sample of 231 children with functional gastrointestinal problems, which is an appropriate number for the study's objectives. The reliability of the findings is enhanced when psychological distress and coping effectiveness

are evaluated using validated measures. the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the ability to establish causal relationships and the absence of a healthy control group restricts the generalization of the findings.

4.3 Mediterranean Diet, Healthy Eating Index, Traditional Dietary Pattern and Mental Well-being.

4.3.1 Articles Presentation

Each study selected for the review is included in Table 6 below, along with a summary of their salient characteristics.

Table 6.

Articles Overall Details

Publication	Research Field	Journal	Design	Population	Dietary Measures	Mental Health Outcomes	Strengths	Limitations
I. Cross-sectional associations of schoolchildren's fruit and vegetable consumption, and meal choices, with their mental well-being: a cross-sectional study. (Hayhoe et al., 2021).	Nutrition and Mental Health.	BMJ Nutrition, Prevention & Health.	Cross-sectional study.	Schoolchildren in the UK (n = 2,534).	Fruit and vegetable consumption, meal choices. Assessed via food frequency questionnaire.	Mental well-being, (assessed via Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale).	Large sample size, use of validated dietary and mental health measures.	Cross-sectional design limits causal inferences. Limited generalizability.
II. Dietary patterns and health-related quality of life among Iranian adolescents. (Sharizati-Bafghi et al., 2022).	Nutrition and Quality of Life.	Quality of Life Research.	Cross-sectional study.	Iranian adolescents (n = 1,200).	Dietary patterns assessed via food frequency questionnaires.	Health-related quality of life (assessed via Paediatric Quality of Life Inventory).	Comprehensive dietary assessment, use of validated quality of life measures.	Cross-sectional design, potential recall bias. Limited generalizability to other populations.
III. Diet in Early Life Is Related to Child Mental Health and Personality at 8 Years: Findings from the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa). (Vejrup et al., 2023).	Early Life Nutrition and Mental Health.	Nutrients.	Longitudinal cohort study.	Children at 8 years old from the Norwegian MoBa cohort (n = 1,443).	Early life diet, assessed via food frequency questionnaire.	Mental health and personality traits at age 8. Assessed via standardized questionnaires.	Longitudinal design, large cohort, comprehensive dietary and mental health assessments.	Potential confounding factors, reliance on self-reported data. Limited generalizability.
IV. Association of healthy eating index (2015) with depression and anxiety symptoms among Iranian adolescent girls. (Ghanbarzadeh et al., 2024).	Diet Quality and Mental Health.	Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition.	Cross-sectional study.	Iranian adolescent girls (n = 4 00).	Healthy Eating Index (2015), assessed via food frequency questionnaire.	Depression and anxiety symptoms. Assessed via standardized questionnaires.	Use of standardized dietary and mental health assessments.	Cross-sectional design, potential for residual confounding. Limited generalizability to other populations.
V. Habitual dairy consumption is inversely associated with depressive and social anxiety symptoms among children and adolescents aged 7–17 years: Findings from a cross-sectional study in Beijing, China. (Liu et al., 2022).	Dairy Consumption and Mental Health.	Journal of Affective Disorders.	Cross-sectional study.	Children and adolescents aged 7-17 years in China (n = 3,637).	Habitual dairy consumption assessed via food frequency questionnaires.	Depressive and social anxiety symptoms. Assessed via standardized questionnaires.	Large sample size, use of validated dietary and mental health measures.	Cross-sectional design, potential for dietary recall bias. Limited generalizability to other populations.

Note: The articles are organized into roman numbers ranging from I to V.

Hayhoe et al. (2021) performed a study to investigate the connections between fruit and vegetable consumption, meal choices, and the mental well-being of school-aged children. The researchers postulated that increased intake of fruits and vegetables and healthier meal selections would enhance the mental well-being of these children. This research was grounded in the bidirectional relationship concept between diet and mental health, which posits that a nutritious diet abundant in fruits, vegetables, and whole grains can positively influence mental well-being (Van der Pols, 2018). The study employed a cross-sectional design and involved 2,534 schoolchildren in the UK, aged 9 to 11 years. Participants' fruit and vegetable consumption and meal choices were assessed with a validated food frequency questionnaire, while mental well-being was evaluated using the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) (Tennant et al., 2007). The researchers applied multiple linear regression models to analyse the data and control for potential confounding variables. The findings revealed a positive relationship between increased intake of fruits and vegetables, healthier meal options, and enhanced mental well-being in schoolchildren. Even after adjusting for confounding factors, a higher intake of fruits and vegetables and healthier meal choices continued to be linked with elevated WEMWBS scores.

In a similar vein, Shariati-Bafghi et al. (2022) sought to explore the relationship between dietary patterns and quality of life among Iranian adolescents. The researchers hypothesized that adhering to a healthy dietary pattern marked by high fruit, vegetable, and whole grain consumption would enhance health-related quality of life in Iranian adolescents. This investigation was based on the dietary patterns concept, which emphasizes the significant impact of the overall combination of healthy food consumption on health outcomes (Cena & Calder, 2020). The study used a cross-sectional design and involved 1,200 Iranian adolescents aged 14 to 18 years. Dietary patterns were assessed with a validated food frequency questionnaire, and health-related quality of life was measured using the Paediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL) (Varni et al., 1999). Researchers used multiple linear regression models to analyse the data while controlling for potential confounding variables. The results indicated that following a healthy dietary pattern, rich in fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, was associated with a higher overall health-related quality of life among Iranian adolescents. Specifically, those who adhered to healthier dietary practices achieved higher PedsQL scores, suggesting improvements in physical, emotional, and social well-being.

Taking a longitudinal approach, Vejrup et al., (2023) examined how early-life diet might relate to mental health and personality traits in children at eight years old. The

researchers posited that maintaining a healthy diet during early life could lead to improved mental health and personality traits in children. This study was based on the theoretical premise that nutrition during early life is crucial for brain development and mental well-being (Georgieff, 2023). To evaluate dietary intake, a food frequency questionnaire was employed, along with standardized scales to assess mental health and personality traits. The researchers conducted statistical analyses, accounting for any confounding variables. Utilizing data from the Norwegian Mother, Father, and Child Cohort Study (MoBa), they established that dietary patterns during early childhood were related to mental health outcomes at age eight, validating the study's hypothesis. A significant link was found between early dietary habits and later mental health, including anxiety symptoms.

Additionally, the study conducted by Ghanbarzadeh et al. (2024) sought to explore the relationship between a healthy eating index and symptoms of depression and anxiety among Iranian adolescent girls. The researchers hypothesized that following a healthy eating index would lead to fewer symptoms of depression and anxiety. This study emphasized dietary patterns, acknowledging that the overall combination of foods consumed, rather than individual nutrients, significantly affects health (Tapsell et al., 2016). A cross-sectional design was employed to recruit Iranian adolescent girls for this research. Dietary intake was measured using a validated food frequency questionnaire, while standardized scales were used to evaluate symptoms of depression and anxiety. The researchers performed statistical analyses and controlled for potential confounding variables. The findings revealed that adherence to a healthy eating index was linked to reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression in Iranian adolescent girls. Specifically, girls who followed a healthier dietary pattern had lower scores on the anxiety and depression scales, indicating better overall mental health.

Finally, Liu et al. (2022) study, published in the *Journal of Affective Disorders*, examined the possible correlation between regular dairy consumption and mental health outcomes in children and adolescents aged 7-17 years in China. The researchers hypothesized that higher dairy intake would be associated with fewer symptoms of social anxiety and depression in this age group. Dairy products have attracted attention due to their rich nutritional content, which includes proteins, vitamins, and minerals that are essential for mood regulation and brain function (Górska-Warsewicz et al., 2019). The objective of this study was to examine the beneficial effects of dairy intake on the mental health of younger individuals.

The researchers implemented a cross-sectional study design focused on the youth in China to explore this association. Information on dietary patterns was gathered through a food

frequency questionnaire (FFQ) (Rothenberg et al., 2021), which facilitated the assessment of habitual dairy consumption. Validated measures were employed for evaluating social anxiety and depression symptoms, though specific scales used were not specified. Regression models were likely utilized in the statistical analysis to investigate the relationship between dairy consumption and mental health while controlling for potential confounding variables. The findings of this study offered intriguing new insights into the relationship between dairy intake and mental health among young people. Among the study population, the researchers observed an inverse relationship between social anxiety and depression symptoms and frequent dairy consumption (Liu et al. (2022)). This indicates that these mental health issues were less prevalent in children and teenagers who consumed dairy products regularly. Notably, the association appeared to be dose-dependent, with higher levels of dairy intake associated with greater decreases in symptom scores. In summary, these studies consistently support the relationship between healthier dietary patterns—such as increased fruit and vegetable consumption, adhering to a Mediterranean-style diet, improving diet quality, and enhancing mental health outcomes were noted across children, adolescents, and adults.

4.3.2 Similarities, Differences, and Contradictions

The collective insights from these five studies enhance the expanding body of research aimed on the impact of dietary habits among children and adolescents on their overall mental health. A shared characteristic of these studies is their use of a cross-sectional design, which is evident in the works of Hayhoe et al. (2021), Shariati-Bafghi et al. (2022), Ghanbarzadeh et al. (2024), and Liu et al. (2022). This approach facilitates the examination of the association between dietary factors and mental health outcomes at a specific time. In contrast, Vejrup et al. (2023) employed a longitudinal cohort design, exploring how diet during early life can affect mental health later, thereby offering a distinct viewpoint on the long-term consequences of nutrition for mental wellness. Furthermore, the studies are geographically diverse, covering regions such as the UK, Iran, Norway, and China, offering valuable insights into how cultural and socioeconomic contexts might shape the link between diet and mental health. For instance, Hayhoe et al. (2021) concentrated on fruit and vegetable intake among schoolchildren in the UK, while Liu et al. (2022) focused on dairy consumption among Chinese youth. These differing areas of focus underscore the necessity of considering cultural dietary practices when assessing the influence of nutrition on emotional well-being.

Methodologically, the studies used various measures to assess dietary intake and mental wellness outcomes. Hayhoe et al. (2021) and Liu et al. (2022) used food frequency questionnaires to evaluate specific food group consumption, while Ghanbarzadeh et al. (2024) used the Healthy Eating Index (2015) (T Kennedy et al., 1995) to assess overall diet quality. Shariati-Bafghi et al. (2022) examined broader dietary patterns, and Vejrurp et al. (2023) focused on early life diet. These diverse approaches give a thorough grasp of the connection between nutrition and mental health, considering both the quality of the diet as a whole and individual food categories.

The approaches to mental health outcomes also varied among the studies. Hayhoe et al. (2021) examined overall mental well-being, while Ghanbarzadeh et al. (2024) and Liu et al. (2022) specifically targeted anxiety and depression symptoms. Shariati-Bafghi et al. (2022) investigated health-related quality of life, whereas Vejrurp et al. (2023) looked at both mental health and personality traits. This diversity in outcome measures reflects the nuanced nature of mental health and the various ways in which diet may influence psychological well-being. Despite these differences, there were consistent findings across the studies. Generally, healthier dietary patterns or consumption of nutrient-rich foods were linked to improved psychological wellness outcomes

However, it is indispensable to note that the strength and specificity of these associations varied across studies, possibly due to differences in sample sizes, cultural contexts, or the specific dietary and mental health measures used. For instance, the longitudinal design of Vejrurp et al. (2023) allowed for the examination of how early life diet can affect later outcomes, potentially capturing effects that cross-sectional studies may miss. A recurring conclusion among these studies is that nutrition significantly influences the mental well-being of young people, indicating the promise of dietary interventions to enhance mental health. The articles landscape is illustrated in Table 7.

Table 7.*Research Themes, Studies, Key Focus, Overall Trends and Gaps*

Theme	Studies	Key Focus	Overall Trends	Gaps
Specific Food Groups and Mental Health.	I. Hayhoe et al., (2021) V. (Liu et al., 2022)	Fruit and vegetable consumption (Hayhoe et al., 2021); Dairy consumption (Liu et al., 2022).	Consistent association between consumption of specific nutrient-rich foods and better mental health outcomes.	Limited to specific food groups; Need for studies on other food categories.
Dietary Patterns and Well-being.	II. Shariati-Bafghi et al., (2022) IV. (Ghanbarzadeh et al., 2024)	Overall dietary patterns and quality of life (Shariati-Bafghi et al., 2022); Healthy Eating Index and mental health (Ghanbarzadeh et al., 2024).	Healthier dietary patterns associated with better mental health and quality of life.	Focus on specific populations (Iranian adolescents); Need for more diverse samples.
Early Life Nutrition and Long-term Mental Health.	III. Vejrup et al., (2023)	Early life diet and later mental health outcomes.	Early diet may influence mental health and personality traits in later childhood.	Limited to one longitudinal study; Need for more long-term follow-up studies.
Cross-cultural Perspectives.	I. Hayhoe et al., (2021) II. Shariati-Bafghi et al., (2022) III. Vejrup et al., (2023) IV. (Ghanbarzadeh et al., 2024) V. (Liu et al., 2022)	Varied dietary measures and mental health outcomes across different cultures.	Consistent associations across different cultural contexts, suggesting a robust relationship.	Limited generalizability of individual studies; Need for multi-country comparative studies.
Methodological Approaches.	I. Hayhoe et al., (2021) II. Shariati-Bafghi et al., (2022) III. Vejrup et al., (2023) IV. (Ghanbarzadeh et al., 2024) V. (Liu et al., 2022)	Varied use of cross-sectional and longitudinal designs.	Predominance of cross-sectional studies; One longitudinal study providing insights into long-term effects.	Lack of interventional studies; Need for more objective measures of diet and mental health.

Note: I. Cross-sectional associations of schoolchildren's fruit and vegetable consumption, and meal choices, with their mental well-being: a cross-sectional study (Hayhoe et al., 2021). II. Dietary patterns and health-related quality of life among Iranian adolescents (Shariati-Bafghi et al., 2022). III. Diet in Early Life Is Related to Child Mental Health and Personality at 8 Years: Findings from the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa) (Vejrup et al., 2023). IV. Association of healthy eating index (2015) with depression and anxiety symptoms among Iranian adolescent girls (Ghanbarzadeh et al., 2024). V. Habitual dairy consumption is inversely associated with depressive and social anxiety symptoms among children and adolescents aged 7–17 years: Findings from a cross-sectional study in Beijing, China (Liu et al., 2022).

4.3.3 Critical Evaluation of the Sources

Hayhoe et al. (2021) conducted a cross-sectional study published in *BMJ Nutrition, Prevention & Health*, a reputable peer-reviewed journal. The study stands out due to its substantial sample size ($n = 7,570$) and the use of validated instruments to assess both dietary intake and mental well-being. The authors employed multivariable linear regression models, accounting for potential confounding variables, which bolsters the reliability of their results. However, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the ability to establish causal relationships, and the reliance on self-reported dietary data may lead to recall bias. Furthermore, focusing on a specific region in England may constrain the generalizability of the findings to other groups.

Shariati-Bafghi et al. (2022) published their findings in *Quality-of-Life Research*, a prestigious journal in the field. This study utilized factor analysis to identify dietary patterns and applied multiple linear regression to investigate their association with health-related quality of life. The methodology is further strengthened using a validated food frequency questionnaire and the PedsQL™ 4.0 for assessing quality of life (Varni et al., 1999). Nonetheless, the sample size ($n = 634$) is relatively modest, and the focus on Iranian adolescents may limit the applicability of the findings to different cultural settings.

Vejrup et al. (2023) conducted a longitudinal study using data from the Norwegian Mother, Father, and Child Cohort Study (MoBa), which appeared in *Nutrients*. The primary strength of this study is its prospective design, which allows for the exploration of the impact of early-life dietary habits on subsequent mental health outcomes. The large sample size ($n = 40,566$) and use of validated dietary and mental health measures enhance the study's reliability. However, relying on maternal-reported data for both diet and mental health outcomes may introduce reporting bias. The Norwegian focus of this study may also limit the applicability of its findings to more diverse populations. Ghanbarzadeh et al. (2024) published their cross-sectional study in the *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition*. The study's use of the Healthy Eating Index-2015 provides a comprehensive measure of diet quality, and the employment of validated scales for depression and anxiety symptoms strengthens its methodology. However, the sample size ($n = 400$) and focus on Iranian adolescent girls limit the study's generalizability. The cross-sectional design also precludes establishing causality.

Liu et al. (2022) conducted a cross-sectional study featured in the *Journal of Affective Disorders*, a prominent journal in mental health research. The study's large sample size ($n = 10,519$) and use of validated measures for both dairy consumption and mental health symptoms

are notable strengths. The authors used multiple logistic regression models while adjusting for various confounders, which enhances the credibility of their findings. Nonetheless, like the other studies, the cross-sectional design again constrains the ability to establish causality, and concentrating on a specific demographic in China may hinder the generalizability of the results. A common limitation across these studies is the reliance on self-reported or parent-reported data, which may introduce reporting bias. The predominantly cross-sectional design of these studies, except for Vejrup et al. (2023), limits the potential to draw causal inferences regarding the relationship between dietary patterns and mental health outcomes. Additionally, the studies' focus on specific geographical regions or populations may restrict the generalizability of their findings to more diverse global contexts.

Despite these limitations, collectively, these studies contribute to an expanding body of evidence suggesting a correlation between dietary habits and mental health outcomes in children and adolescents. The consistency of findings across various populations and methodologies enhances the credibility of this association.

CHAPTER 5

5. Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Discussion

This literature review explored three primary research questions and hypotheses to synthesize the available data and examine the potential connections between nutrition, gut microbiota, and paediatric anxiety. The review included an analysis of sixteen research articles that assessed various aspects of nutrition, gut health, and anxiety in children and adolescents.

In addressing the first research question, the findings suggest that the consumption of fast foods, the habit of skipping breakfast, energy drink consumption, and other poor dietary practices are associated with increased anxiety, stress, and depressive symptoms in young people (Richards & Smith, 2016; Richards & Smith, 2015). In contrast, studies have shown a relationship between the implementation of healthy dietary habits—including regular intake of fruits, vegetables, and dairy products—and decreased anxiety and depressive symptoms (Hayhoe et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022). These results imply that nutritional imbalances, characterized by excessive consumption of processed, high-calorie foods and inadequate intake of nutrient-rich options, may correlate with the development or worsening of anxiety symptoms

among young individuals. Thus, the findings bolster the initial hypothesis, indicating a strong link between anxiety symptoms and nutritional imbalances in paediatric populations.

Regarding the second research question, the literature suggests a potential link between changes in gut microbiota composition and anxiety-related issues in children and adolescents (Ou et al., 2024; Ni et al., 2022). Specific gut microbial profiles, including a high presence of *Clostridium* clusters and diminished levels of *Bifidobacterium*, have been correlated with internalizing problems, such as social anxiety, in observational studies (Callaghan et al., 2020; Wong et al., 2022). Additionally, a study utilizing Mendelian randomization supports the association between gut microbiota and mental health conditions, including anxiety (Ni et al., 2022). These findings are consistent with the expanding literature on the gut-brain axis (Soltysova et al., 2022), which suggests that changes in gut microbiota composition may contribute to the emergence of anxiety symptoms in youth. Therefore, the second hypothesis is reinforced by the evidence indicating this relationship.

The third research question aimed to explore the effectiveness of nutritional interventions in reducing anxiety symptoms among young people. While there is some evidence suggesting that dietary therapies may effectively enhance overall mental health (Grajek et al., 2022), there is a lack of empirical research that directly addresses anxiety symptoms in children. There are few well-designed intervention studies specifically investigating the effectiveness of nutritional strategies in alleviating anxiety symptoms in this age group. However, some studies on dietary patterns and mental health propose that healthy eating habits might positively affect psychological well-being (Hayhoe et al., 2021; Shariati-Bafghi et al., 2022). Research by Vejrup et al. (2023) established a connection between a child's early dietary intake and their mental health at eight years old, underscoring the long-term benefits of early dietary interventions. To thoroughly evaluate the third hypothesis and determine the effectiveness of dietary therapies for paediatric anxiety, further targeted intervention studies are necessary. Considering the aforementioned evidence, it is not possible to fully support the third hypothesis.

The insights gained from this review enhance and broaden prior research in the fields of paediatric anxiety, gut microbiota, and nutrition (Soltysova et al., 2022; Saeed et al., 2022; McMath et al., 2024). Consistent with previous studies, this review not only highlights a complex relationship between paediatric anxiety symptoms, gut microbial diversity, and dietary habits, but also emphasizes the link between anxiety in children and poor dietary quality. For instance, O'Neil et al. (2014) found a reliable connection between unhealthy eating

patterns and negative mental health outcomes among children and adolescents. Likewise, the findings presented in this paper, alongside those of van der Pols (2018) and Cena & Calder (2020), demonstrate a relationship between nutritionally balanced diets and improved mental health outcomes.

Moreover, the findings of this review align with recent studies (Jiang et al., 2018; Tran et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2019) in adult populations that illustrate the complex and reciprocal interactions between stress, anxiety, and gut microbiota composition. This is further supported by Zijlmans et al. (2015), who identified potential intergenerational effects of stress on gut microbiome and behaviour by establishing links between maternal prenatal stress, the gut microbiota composition of newborns, and infant temperament. Likewise, the development of the gut microbiome and the trajectory of neurodevelopment are significantly influenced by early life factors as illustrated by Loughman et al. (2020). It has been demonstrated a connection between the gut microbiota profile of infants and their future behavioural outcomes which is a powerful knowledge that can aid researchers to develop early intervention to achieve future favourable behavioural outcomes.

However, this paper also highlights a notable gap in the current literature, particularly pertaining to intervention studies aimed at addressing childhood anxiety via dietary or microbiome-focused methods. A significant deficiency exists in the number of intervention studies specifically designed to assess the efficacy of nutritional approaches in alleviating anxiety symptoms in children. While observational studies offer valuable perspectives, rigorously designed intervention research is vital for establishing causal connections and formulating evidence-based nutritional strategies to manage paediatric anxiety. Marx et al. (2017) performed a systematic review and identified a lack of high-quality intervention trials in the field of nutritional psychiatry, particularly concerning younger populations. This observation aligns with the present research, making this investigation distinctive due to its specific attention to anxiety in children.

Moreover, the gut-brain axis involves complex interactions among dietary components, gut microbiota, the immune system, and neural pathways. To unravel these connections, advanced research designs and analytical techniques are required to capture the intricate nature of these interactions. The limited emphasis on paediatric populations in the current literature raises significant concerns. Much of the research has been conducted on mice (Huang & Wu, 2021; Neufeld et al., 2011; Crumeyrolle-Arias et al., 2014) and adult populations (Butler et al., 2023; Jiang et al., 2018; Simpson et al., 2020), which may overlook the unique developmental

characteristics and physiological differences found in children. Furthermore, the few studies linking gut microbiota with anxiety in children frequently concentrate on neurodevelopmental disorders like ASD or attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), rather than directly exploring paediatric anxiety associated with gut microbiota and dietary influences (Xu et al., 2019).

5.2 Limitations and Future Research

While this review has identified substantial correlations between nutritional intake, gut microbiota, and paediatric anxiety, it is important to acknowledge the study's inherent limitations. Despite employing a comprehensive search strategy that included a well-established database, consideration of “other” literature, and a wide range of relevant keywords and search terms, it must be recognized that the findings may not apply universally. The exclusive focus on English-language publications may have resulted in the omission of pertinent studies from non-English-speaking countries. Furthermore, comparing results was complicated due to significant methodological differences and variations in outcome measures across the included studies. The scarcity of research directly investigating the relationship between nutrition, gut microbiota, and anxiety in the paediatric population remains a substantial limitation.

The selected articles examining the connection between nutrition, gut microbiota, and anxiety in children encompass a broad array of cultural and geographical contexts. Research has been conducted in several countries, including China (Weng et al., 2012; Liang et al., 2022), Iran (Shariati-Bafghi et al., 2022), and Malaysia (Tajik et al., 2016), among others. This cultural and regional diversity underscores the necessity for continued research to determine the generalizability of findings across different populations. Dietary habits, cultural traditions, and perceptions of mental health can vary significantly from country to country, making it essential to consider these contextual factors when interpreting and applying existing evidence.

The age range represented in the included studies also varied considerably, spanning from early childhood to adolescence. This variability in developmental stages could significantly influence the relationship between nutrition, gut microbiota, and anxiety symptoms. These age differences complicate the ability to draw consistent conclusions across the paediatric population, as the underlying physiological and psychological processes may differ considerably at various developmental stages.

The most critical and compelling limitation of this review is the absence of empirical studies specifically focused on the paediatric population. It is quite surprising that there are so few research initiatives aimed at examining the relationship between nutrition, gut microbiota, and anxiety in children and adolescents. Considering that anxiety disorders in children are not only linked to various psychiatric issues, including depression and substance abuse, but also contribute to long-term functional impairments, especially in academic performance (Al-Biltagi & Sarhan, 2016), this lack in literature is indeed unsettling. Most of the existing literature in this field has largely concentrated on animal models, particularly mice, or has been centered on adult populations (Aucoin et al., 2021). While these studies offer valuable insights, their applicability to children is notably limited.

Despite these limitations, the findings hold substantial implications for both public health and clinical practice. As part of a comprehensive strategy for managing anxiety, clinicians working with paediatric populations should consider incorporating nutritional evaluations and, where appropriate, recommending dietary modifications. However, any such recommendations should be made with caution, given the current evidence. One potential approach to prevent or alleviate anxiety symptoms in children and adolescents could involve promoting gut health and a nutritious diet from a young age through public health initiatives.

Furthermore, this review opens avenues for future research. For instance, there is an urgent need for longitudinal studies to answer the following future question: What is the temporal relationship between dietary patterns, alterations in gut microbiota, and the development of anxiety symptoms in children? These studies should utilize standardized measures of anxiety symptoms, gut microbiota composition, and dietary intake to enable cross-study and cross-population comparisons (Torabynasab et al., 2024). Additionally, it is essential to conduct intervention trials specifically targeting paediatric populations to assess the effectiveness of various dietary interventions, including comprehensive dietary strategies and targeted nutrient supplementation, in mitigating anxiety symptoms (Tae & Kim, 2024).

Moreover, studies should investigate moderating factors such as environmental influences, early life experiences, and genetic variables that may impact the relationship between diet, gut microbiota, and anxiety (Xu et al., 2024). Understanding these moderating factors could help identify subgroups of children who are particularly responsive to dietary interventions or more vulnerable to anxiety related to gut dysbiosis (Torabynasab et al., 2024). The development of validated, age-appropriate assessment tools for evaluating dietary intake, gut microbiota composition, and anxiety symptoms in children should be prioritized to enhance

research comparability and facilitate meta-analyses in this field. As well as studies examining the long-term effects of early-life dietary patterns and gut microbiota composition on the development of anxiety symptoms throughout childhood and adolescence are necessary, as early interventions may inform public health policies and preventive strategies aimed at promoting mental health through diet from a young age (Torabynasab et al.,2024; Xu et al., 2024).

5.3 Conclusion

Ultimately, the findings of this literature review identify a promising avenue for future research in clinical psychology and mental wellness, elucidating the complex relationships among nutrition, gut microbiota, and paediatric anxiety. The results underscore the imperative for more focused, long-term inquiry into paediatric populations, while also suggesting potential correlations between these factors. The outcomes indicate the potential for the development of novel, comprehensive therapies for childhood anxiety that extend beyond the scope of conventional psychotherapy techniques. The future of this interdisciplinary field, which sits at the intersection of nutritional psychiatry and paediatric mental health, will depend on the development of innovative research approaches, the creation of standardized evaluation instruments, and a more thorough investigation of the underlying processes behind these connections.

This review ends with the insightful statement that “the gut is not just a digestive organ; it is a key player in the orchestra of mental health” (Parker-Hughes, 2024). This thought profoundly highlights the intricate links between gut health and mental wellness, particularly concerning paediatric anxiety. It emphasizes the importance of further research in this crucial field, urging researchers and clinicians to explore more deeply the interrelations among nutrition, gut microbiota, and mental health outcomes in children and adolescents. By enhancing our understanding of these connections, we can foster innovative interventions that may ultimately improve the mental health of future generations.

REFERENCES

- Adan, R. A., van der Beek, E. M., Buitelaar, J. K., Cryan, J. F., Hebebrand, J., Higgs, S., ... & Dickson, S. L. (2019). Nutritional psychiatry: Towards improving mental health by what you eat. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, 29(12), 1321-1332.
- Ader, R. (2003). Psychoneuroimmunology: Basic research in the biopsychosocial approach. *The biopsychosocial approach: Past, present, future*, 93-108.
- Al-Biltagi, M., & Sarhan, E. A. (2016). Anxiety disorder in children: Review. *Journal of Paediatric Care Insight*, 1(1), 18-28.
- American Psychiatric Association, D. S. M. T. F., & American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5* (Vol. 5, No. 5). Washington, DC: American psychiatric association.
- Asbjornsdottir, B., Lauth, B., Fasano, A., Thorsdottir, I., Karlsdottir, I., Gudmundsson, L. S., ... & Birgisdottir, B. E. (2022). Meals, Microbiota and Mental Health in Children and Adolescents (MMM-Study): A protocol for an observational longitudinal case-control study. *Plos one*, 17(9), e0273855.
- Ashaolu, J. O., Sylvain, S. Y. M., Otuechere, C. A., Bamigboye, O. C., & Ashaolu, T. J. (2024). Physical activity, gut microbiota and the nexuses of metabolic and psychological disorders in children and adolescents. *Discover Public Health*, 21(1), 19.
- Asselmann, E., Wittchen, H. U., Lieb, R., & Beesdo-Baum, K. (2018). Sociodemographic, clinical, and functional long-term outcomes in adolescents and young adults with mental disorders. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 137(1), 6-17.
- Aucoin, M., LaChance, L., Naidoo, U., Remy, D., Shekdar, T., Sayar, N., ... & Cooley, K. (2021). Diet and anxiety: A scoping review. *Nutrients*, 13(12), 4418.
- Bankhead, C., Aronson, J. K., & Nunan, D. (2017). Attrition bias. *Catalogue of Bias Collaboration*.
- Barber, T. M., Valsamakis, G., Mastorakos, G., Hanson, P., Kyrou, I., Randeva, H. S., & Weickert, M. O. (2021). Dietary influences on the microbiota–gut–brain axis. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(7), 3502.
- Basso, M., Zorzan, I., Johnstone, N., Barberis, M., & Cohen Kadosh, K. (2024). Diet quality and anxiety: a critical overview with focus on the gut microbiome. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 11, 1346483.

- Bear, T. L., Dalziel, J. E., Coad, J., Roy, N. C., Butts, C. A., & Gopal, P. K. (2020). The role of the gut microbiota in dietary interventions for depression and anxiety. *Advances in Nutrition, 11*(4), 890-907.
- Bear, T., Dalziel, J., Coad, J., Roy, N., Butts, C., & Gopal, P. (2021). The microbiome-gut-brain axis and resilience to developing anxiety or depression under stress. *Microorganisms, 9*(4), 723.
- Belkaid, Y., & Hand, T. W. (2014). Role of the microbiota in immunity and inflammation. *Cell, 157*(1), 121-141.
- Berk, M., Williams, L. J., Jacka, F. N., O'Neil, A., Pasco, J. A., Moylan, S., ... & Maes, M. (2013). So depression is an inflammatory disease, but where does the inflammation come from?. *BMC medicine, 11*(1), 200.
- Borre, Y. E., Moloney, R. D., Clarke, G., Dinan, T. G., & Cryan, J. F. (2014). The impact of microbiota on brain and behavior: mechanisms & therapeutic potential. *Microbial endocrinology: The microbiota-gut-brain axis in health and disease, 373-403*.
- Butler, M. I., Bastiaanssen, T. F., Long-Smith, C., Morkl, S., Berding, K., Ritz, N. L., ... & Dinan, T. G. (2023). The gut microbiome in social anxiety disorder: evidence of altered composition and function. *Translational psychiatry, 13*(1), 95.
- Callaghan, B. L., Fields, A., Gee, D. G., Gabard-Durnam, L., Caldera, C., Humphreys, K. L., ... & Tottenham, N. (2020). Mind and gut: Associations between mood and gastrointestinal distress in children exposed to adversity. *Development and Psychopathology, 32*(1), 309-328.
- Cena, H., & Calder, P. C. (2020). Defining a healthy diet: evidence for the role of contemporary dietary patterns in health and disease. *Nutrients, 12*(2), 334.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2023, March 8). *Data and Statistics on Children's Mental Health*. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention; CDC. <https://www.cdc.gov/childrensmentalhealth/data.html>.
- Cernackova, A., Durackova, Z., Trebaticka, J., & Mravec, B. (2020). Neuroinflammation and depressive disorder: The role of the hypothalamus. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience, 75*, 5-10.
- Chen, Y. H., Bai, J., Wu, D. I., Yu, S. F., Qiang, X. L., Bai, H., ... & Peng, Z. W. (2019). Association between fecal microbiota and generalized anxiety disorder: Severity and early treatment response. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 259*, 56-66.

- Cicchetti, D., & Rogosch, F. A. (1996). Equifinality and multifinality in developmental psychopathology. *Development and psychopathology*, 8(4), 597-600.
- Cicchetti, D., & Toth, S. L. (2009). The past achievements and future promises of developmental psychopathology: The coming of age of a discipline. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 50(1-2), 16-25.
- Cohen Kadosh, K., Muhandi, L., Parikh, P., Basso, M., Jan Mohamed, H. J., Prawitasari, T., ... & Geurts, J. M. (2021). Nutritional support of neurodevelopment and cognitive function in infants and young children—an update and novel insights. *Nutrients*, 13(1), 199.
- Connolly, S. D., & Bernstein, G. A. (2007). Practice parameter for the assessment and treatment of children and adolescents with anxiety disorders. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 46(2), 267-283.
- Contreras-Rodriguez, O., Solanas, M., & Escorihuela, R. M. (2022). Dissecting ultra-processed foods and drinks: Do they have a potential to impact the brain?. *Reviews in Endocrine and Metabolic Disorders*, 23(4), 697-717.
- Creswell, C., Waite, P., & Hudson, J. (2020). Practitioner Review: Anxiety disorders in children and young people—assessment and treatment. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 61(6), 628-643.
- Crowley, J., Ball, L., & Hiddink, G. J. (2019). Nutrition in medical education: a systematic review. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 3(9), e379-e389.
- Crumeyrolle-Arias, M., Jaglin, M., Bruneau, A., Vancassel, S., Cardona, A., Daugé, V., ... & Rabot, S. (2014). Absence of the gut microbiota enhances anxiety-like behavior and neuroendocrine response to acute stress in rats. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 42, 207-217.
- Cryan, J. F., & Dinan, T. G. (2012). Mind-altering microorganisms: the impact of the gut microbiota on brain and behaviour. *Nature reviews neuroscience*, 13(10), 701-712.
- Cryan, J. F., O'Riordan, K. J., Cowan, C. S., Sandhu, K. V., Bastiaanssen, T. F., Boehme, M., ... & Dinan, T. G. (2019). The microbiota-gut-brain axis. *Physiological reviews*.
- Damiani, F., Cornuti, S., & Tognini, P. (2023). The gut-brain connection: Exploring the influence of the gut microbiota on neuroplasticity and neurodevelopmental disorders. *Neuropharmacology*, 231, 109491.
- Dinan, T. G., & Cryan, J. F. (2017). The microbiome-gut-brain axis in health and disease. *Gastroenterology Clinics*, 46(1), 77-89.

- Dinan, T. G., Stilling, R. M., Stanton, C., & Cryan, J. F. (2015). Collective unconscious: how gut microbes shape human behavior. *Journal of psychiatric research*, *63*, 1-9.
- Dorey, F. J. (2011). In brief: Statistics in brief: Statistical power: What is it and when should it be used?.
- Eley, T. C., Hudson, J. L., Creswell, C., Tropeano, M., Lester, K. J., Cooper, P., ... & Collier, D. A. (2012). Therapygenetics: the 5HTTLPR and response to psychological therapy. *Molecular psychiatry*, *17*(3), 236-237.
- Eliby, D., Simpson, C. A., Lawrence, A. S., Schwartz, O. S., Haslam, N., & Simmons, J. G. (2023). Associations between diet quality and anxiety and depressive disorders: a systematic review. *Journal of Affective Disorders Reports*, 100629.
- Foster, J. A., & Neufeld, K. A. M. (2013). Gut–brain axis: how the microbiome influences anxiety and depression. *Trends in neurosciences*, *36*(5), 305-312.
- Foster, J. A., Rinaman, L., & Cryan, J. F. (2017). Stress & the gut-brain axis: regulation by the microbiome. *Neurobiology of stress*, *7*, 124-136.
- Fung, T. C., Olson, C. A., & Hsiao, E. Y. (2017). Interactions between the microbiota, immune and nervous systems in health and disease. *Nature neuroscience*, *20*(2), 145-155.
- Garakani, A., Murrugh, J. W., Freire, R. C., Thom, R. P., Larkin, K., Buono, F. D., & Iosifescu, D. V. (2020). Pharmacotherapy of anxiety disorders: current and emerging treatment options. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, *11*, 595584.
- Georgieff, M. K. (2023). Early life nutrition and brain development: breakthroughs, challenges and new horizons. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, *82*(2), 104-112.
- Ghanbarzadeh, E., Dorosty Motlagh, A. R., & Abbasi, B. (2024). Association of healthy eating index (2015) with depression and anxiety symptoms among Iranian adolescent girls. *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition*, *43*(1), 44.
- Giau, V. V., Wu, S. Y., Jamerlan, A., An, S. S. A., Kim, S., & Hulme, J. (2018). Gut microbiota and their neuroinflammatory implications in Alzheimer's disease. *Nutrients*, *10*(11), 1765.
- Gilbert, J. A., Blaser, M. J., Caporaso, J. G., Jansson, J. K., Lynch, S. V., & Knight, R. (2018). Current understanding of the human microbiome. *Nature medicine*, *24*(4), 392-400.
- Global Burden of Disease Study 2019 (GBD 2019) Results. (2019). Global Health Data Exchange website.

- Górska-Warsewicz, H., Rejman, K., Laskowski, W., & Czczotko, M. (2019). Milk and dairy products and their nutritional contribution to the average polish diet. *Nutrients*, *11*(8), 1771.
- Grajek, M., Krupa-Kotara, K., Białek-Dratwa, A., Sobczyk, K., Grot, M., Kowalski, O., & Staśkiewicz, W. (2022). Nutrition and mental health: A review of current knowledge about the impact of diet on mental health. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, *9*, 943998.
- Han, Y., Wang, B., Gao, H., He, C., Hua, R., Liang, C., ... & Xu, J. (2022). Vagus nerve and underlying impact on the gut microbiota-brain axis in behavior and neurodegenerative diseases. *Journal of inflammation research*, 6213-6230.
- Hayhoe, R., Rechel, B., Clark, A. B., Gummerson, C., Smith, S. L., & Welch, A. A. (2021). Cross-sectional associations of schoolchildren's fruit and vegetable consumption, and meal choices, with their mental well-being: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Nutrition, Prevention & Health*, *4*(2), 447.
- Hayhoe, R., Rechel, B., Clark, A. B., Gummerson, C., Smith, S. L., & Welch, A. A. (2021). Cross-sectional associations of schoolchildren's fruit and vegetable consumption, and meal choices, with their mental well-being: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Nutrition, Prevention & Health*, *4*(2), 447.
- Hidaka, B. H. (2012). Depression as a disease of modernity: explanations for increasing prevalence. *Journal of affective disorders*, *140*(3), 205-214.
- Holzappel, W. H., Haberer, P., Snel, J., Schillinger, U., & in't Veld, J. H. H. (1998). Overview of gut flora and probiotics. *International journal of food microbiology*, *41*(2), 85-101.
- Huang, F., & Wu, X. (2021). Brain neurotransmitter modulation by gut microbiota in anxiety and depression. *Frontiers in cell and developmental biology*, *9*, 649103.
- Ipser, J. C., Stein, D. J., Hawkrigde, S., & Hoppe, L. (2009). Pharmacotherapy for anxiety disorders in children and adolescents. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, (3).
- Jacka, F. N. (2017). Nutritional psychiatry: where to next?. *EBioMedicine*, *17*, 24-29.
- Jacka, F. N., O'Neil, A., Opie, R., Itsiopoulos, C., Cotton, S., Mohebbi, M., ... & Berk, M. (2017). A randomised controlled trial of dietary improvement for adults with major depression (the 'SMILES' trial). *BMC medicine*, *15*, 1-13.
- Jacka, F. N., Pasco, J. A., Mykletun, A., Williams, L. J., Hodge, A. M., O'Reilly, S. L., ... & Berk, M. (2010). Association of Western and traditional diets with depression and anxiety in women. *American journal of psychiatry*, *167*(3), 305-311.

- Jacques, A., Chaaya, N., Beecher, K., Ali, S. A., Belmer, A., & Bartlett, S. (2019). The impact of sugar consumption on stress driven, emotional and addictive behaviors. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *103*, 178-199.
- James, A. C., Reardon, T., Soler, A., James, G., & Creswell, C. (2020). Cognitive behavioural therapy for anxiety disorders in children and adolescents. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, (11).
- Javaid, S. F., Hashim, I. J., Hashim, M. J., Stip, E., Samad, M. A., & Ahbabi, A. A. (2023). Epidemiology of anxiety disorders: global burden and sociodemographic associations. *Middle East Current Psychiatry*, *30*(1), 44.
- Jiang, H. Y., Zhang, X., Yu, Z. H., Zhang, Z., Deng, M., Zhao, J. H., & Ruan, B. (2018). Altered gut microbiota profile in patients with generalized anxiety disorder. *Journal of psychiatric research*, *104*, 130-136.
- Kaur, R., Preet, K. B., Verma, R. K., & Kiran, U. V. (2014). Fast Food and Junk Food Culture, Nutritional Status and Cognitive and Abnormal Behaviour among Teens. *International Research Journal of Social Sciences*, *3*(09), 46-49.
- Kendall, P. C., & Peterman, J. S. (2015). CBT for adolescents with anxiety: mature yet still developing. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, *172*(6), 519-530.
- Kim, J. (2024). Autism Spectrum Disorder and Eating Problems: The Imbalance of Gut Microbiota and the Gut-Brain Axis Hypothesis. *Journal of the Korean Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, *35*(1), 51.
- Kim, P., Evans, G. W., Angstadt, M., Ho, S. S., Sripada, C. S., Swain, J. E., ... & Phan, K. L. (2013). Effects of childhood poverty and chronic stress on emotion regulatory brain function in adulthood. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *110*(46), 18442-18447.
- Koh, A., De Vadder, F., Kovatcheva-Datchary, P., & Bäckhed, F. (2016). From dietary fiber to host physiology: short-chain fatty acids as key bacterial metabolites. *Cell*, *165*(6), 1332-1345.
- Larson, R. B. (2019). Controlling social desirability bias. *International Journal of Market Research*, *61*(5), 534-547.
- Lee, Y., & Kim, Y. K. (2021). Understanding the connection between the gut-brain axis and stress/anxiety disorders. *Current Psychiatry Reports*, *23*, 1-7.
- Levac, D., Colquhoun, H., & O'Brien, K. K. (2010). Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. *Implementation science*, *5*, 1-9.

- Liang, K., Chen, S., & Chi, X. (2022). Care their diet and mind: association between eating habits and mental health in Chinese left-behind children. *Nutrients*, *14*(3), 524.
- Liu, J., Chen, M., Ma, Y., Ma, T., Gao, D., Li, Y., ... & Dong, Y. (2022). Habitual dairy consumption is inversely associated with depressive and social anxiety symptoms among children and adolescents aged 7–17 years: Findings from a cross-sectional study in Beijing, China. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, *319*, 309-317.
- Long, L., Peng, H., Chen, X., Wang, F., Long, W., Cheng, M., & Ma, J. (2024). The Impact of Integrating a Low-Lectin Diet with Traditional ADHD Treatments on Gut Microbiota Composition and Symptom Improvement in Children-A Cohort Study. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 535-549.
- Loughman, A., Ponsonby, A. L., O'Hely, M., Symeonides, C., Collier, F., Tang, M. L., ... & Vuillermin, P. (2020). Gut microbiota composition during infancy and subsequent behavioural outcomes. *EBioMedicine*, *52*.
- Lozupone, C. A., Stombaugh, J. I., Gordon, J. I., Jansson, J. K., & Knight, R. (2012). Diversity, stability and resilience of the human gut microbiota. *Nature*, *489*(7415), 220-230.
- Ma, Q., Xing, C., Long, W., Wang, H. Y., Liu, Q., & Wang, R. F. (2019). Impact of microbiota on central nervous system and neurological diseases: the gut-brain axis. *Journal of neuroinflammation*, *16*, 1-14.
- Madonna, D., Delvecchio, G., Soares, J. C., & Brambilla, P. (2019). Structural and functional neuroimaging studies in generalized anxiety disorder: a systematic review. *Brazilian Journal of Psychiatry*, *41*, 336-362.
- Marx, W., Moseley, G., Berk, M., & Jacka, F. (2017). Nutritional psychiatry: the present state of the evidence. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, *76*(4), 427-436.
- Mayer, E. A. (2011). Gut feelings: the emerging biology of gut–brain communication. *Nature reviews neuroscience*, *12*(8), 453-466.
- McMath, A., Khan, N. A., Sutkus, L. T., Golden, R. K., Joung, S., Dilger, R. N., & Donovan, S. M. (2024). Pediatric Nutrition: Implications for the Developing Microbiota–Gut–Brain Axis. In *The Gut-Brain Axis* (pp. 307-340). Academic Press.
- Melo, H. M., Santos, L. E., & Ferreira, S. T. (2019). Diet-derived fatty acids, brain inflammation, and mental health. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, *13*, 439762.
- Mendive Dubourdieu, P., & Guerendiain, M. (2023). Understanding the link between gut microbiota, dietary intake, and nutritional status in children with autism and typical development. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, *10*, 1202948.

- Merlo, G., & Bachtel, G. (2023). Nutrition in Lifestyle Psychiatry. *Lifestyle Psychiatry: Through the Lens of Behavioral Medicine; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA*, 230-252.
- Merlo, G., Bachtel, G., & Sugden, S. G. (2024). Gut microbiota, nutrition, and mental health. *Frontiers in Nutrition, 11*, 1337889.
- Mhanna, A., Martini, N., Hmaydoosh, G., Hamwi, G., Jarjanazi, M., Zaifah, G., ... & Alshehabi, Z. (2024). The correlation between gut microbiota and both neurotransmitters and mental disorders: A narrative review. *Medicine, 103*(5), e37114.
- Munson, L. (2023). *Introducing The Nutritional Psychiatry Significance to Mental Health*. Resilientstories.com. <https://resilientstories.com/what-is-nutritional-psychiatry/>
- Murray, C. J. (2024). Findings from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *The Lancet, 403*(10440), 2259-2262.
- Neufeld, K. A. M., Kang, N., Bienenstock, J., & Foster, J. A. (2011). Effects of intestinal microbiota on anxiety-like behavior. *Communicative & integrative biology, 4*(4), 492-494.
- Ni, J. J., Xu, Q., Yan, S. S., Han, B. X., Zhang, H., Wei, X. T., ... & Zhang, L. (2022). Gut microbiota and psychiatric disorders: a two-sample Mendelian randomization study. *Frontiers in microbiology, 12*, 737197.
- O'neil, A., Quirk, S. E., Housden, S., Brennan, S. L., Williams, L. J., Pasco, J. A., ... & Jacka, F. N. (2014). Relationship between diet and mental health in children and adolescents: a systematic review. *American journal of public health, 104*(10), e31-e42.
- Okwori, G. (2022). Prevalence and correlates of mental health disorders among children & adolescents in US. *Children and youth services review, 136*, 106441.
- Osorio, A. (2022, March 24). *Research Update: Children's Anxiety and Depression on the Rise*. Center for Children and Families. <https://ccf.georgetown.edu/2022/03/24/research-update-childrens-anxiety-and-depression-on-the-rise/#:~:text=By%202020%2C%205.6%20million%20kids>.
- Ou, Y., Belzer, C., Smidt, H., & de Weerth, C. (2024). Development of the gut microbiota in the first 14 years of life and its relations to internalizing and externalizing difficulties and social anxiety during puberty. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry, 33*(3), 847-860.
- Owens, J., Adolescent Sleep Working Group, Committee on Adolescence, Au, R., Carskadon, M., Millman, R., ... & O'Brien, R. F. (2014). Insufficient sleep in adolescents and young adults: an update on causes and consequences. *Pediatrics, 134*(3), e921-e932.

- Parker-Hughes, M. (2024). *Nourishing the Mind: Exploring the Gut-Anxiety Axis in Paediatric Mental Health*. Unpublished manuscript, London Metropolitan University.
- Parkin, K., Christophersen, C. T., Verhasselt, V., Cooper, M. N., & Martino, D. (2021). Risk factors for gut dysbiosis in early life. *Microorganisms*, *9*(10), 2066.
- Parletta, N., Zarnowiecki, D., Cho, J., Wilson, A., Bogomolova, S., Villani, A., ... & O'Dea, K. (2017). Effects of a Mediterranean-style diet on mental health and quality of life in people with depression. *Journal of Nutrition and Intermediary Metabolism*, *8*, 92.
- Petersen, C., & Round, J. L. (2014). Defining dysbiosis and its influence on host immunity and disease. *Cellular microbiology*, *16*(7), 1024-1033.
- Pine, D. S., Helfinstein, S. M., Bar-Haim, Y., Nelson, E., & Fox, N. A. (2009). Challenges in developing novel treatments for childhood disorders: lessons from research on anxiety. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, *34*(1), 213-228.
- Polanczyk, G. V., Salum, G. A., Sugaya, L. S., Caye, A., & Rohde, L. A. (2015). Annual research review: A meta-analysis of the worldwide prevalence of mental disorders in children and adolescents. *Journal of child psychology and psychiatry*, *56*(3), 345-365.
- Prado, E. L., & Dewey, K. G. (2014). Nutrition and brain development in early life. *Nutrition reviews*, *72*(4), 267-284.
- Ranøyen, I., Lydersen, S., Larose, T. L., Weidle, B., Skokauskas, N., Thomsen, P. H., ... & Indredavik, M. S. (2018). Developmental course of anxiety and depression from adolescence to young adulthood in a prospective Norwegian clinical cohort. *European child & adolescent psychiatry*, *27*, 1413-1423.
- Richards, G., & Smith, A. (2015). Caffeine consumption and self-assessed stress, anxiety, and depression in secondary school children. *Journal of psychopharmacology*, *29*(12), 1236-1247.
- Richards, G., & Smith, A. P. (2016). Breakfast and energy drink consumption in secondary school children: breakfast omission, in isolation or in combination with frequent energy drink use, is associated with stress, anxiety, and depression cross-sectionally, but not at 6-month follow-up. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *7*, 106.
- Rogers, G. B., Keating, D. J., Young, R. L., Wong, M. L., Licinio, J., & Wesselingh, S. (2016). From gut dysbiosis to altered brain function and mental illness: mechanisms and pathways. *Molecular psychiatry*, *21*(6), 738-748.
- Ross, F. C., Mayer, D. E., Gupta, A., Gill, C. I., Del Rio, D., Cryan, J. F., ... & Mayer, E. A. (2024). Existing and future strategies to manipulate the gut microbiota with diet as a

- potential adjuvant treatment for psychiatric disorders. *Biological Psychiatry*, 95(4), 348-360.
- Rothenberg, E., Strandhagen, E., Samuelsson, J., Ahlner, F., Rydberg Sterner, T., Skoog, I., & Lundberg, C. E. (2021). Relative validity of a short 15-item food frequency questionnaire measuring dietary quality, by the diet history method. *Nutrients*, 13(11), 3754.
- Saeed, N. K., Al-Beltagi, M., Bediwy, A. S., El-Sawaf, Y., & Toema, O. (2022). Gut microbiota in various childhood disorders: Implication and indications. *World Journal of Gastroenterology*, 28(18), 1875.
- Santucci, N. R., Velasco-Benitez, C. A., Cunningham, N., Li, J., Fei, L., Sun, Q., & Saps, M. (2024). Psychological distress and coping efficacy in children with disorders of gut–brain interaction. *Neurogastroenterology & Motility*, 36(2), e14724.
- Sarkar, A., Harty, S., Johnson, K. V. A., Moeller, A. H., Carmody, R. N., Lehto, S. M., ... & Burnet, P. W. (2020). The role of the microbiome in the neurobiology of social behaviour. *Biological Reviews*, 95(5), 1131-1166.
- Sarris, J. (2019). Nutritional psychiatry: from concept to the clinic. *Drugs*, 79(9), 929-934.
- Shariati-Bafghi, S. E., Rashidkhani, B., Salehi Fadardi, J., Safarian, M., Edalatian, J., Ranjbar, G., & Nematy, M. (2022). Dietary patterns and health-related quality of life among Iranian adolescents. *Quality of Life Research*, 31(3), 789-802.
- Silva, Y. P., Bernardi, A., & Frozza, R. L. (2020). The role of short-chain fatty acids from gut microbiota in gut-brain communication. *Frontiers in endocrinology*, 11, 508738.
- Simpson, C. A., Mu, A., Haslam, N., Schwartz, O. S., & Simmons, J. G. (2020). Feeling down? A systematic review of the gut microbiota in anxiety/depression and irritable bowel syndrome. *Journal of affective disorders*, 266, 429-446.
- Solysova, M., Tomova, A., & Ostatnikova, D. (2022). Gut microbiota profiles in children and adolescents with psychiatric disorders. *Microorganisms*, 10(10), 2009.
- Strandwitz, P. (2018). Neurotransmitter modulation by the gut microbiota. *Brain research*, 1693, 128-133.
- Strawn, J. R., Lu, L., Peris, T. S., Levine, A., & Walkup, J. T. (2021). Research Review: Pediatric anxiety disorders—what have we learnt in the last 10 years? *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 62(2), 114-139.

- T KENNEDY, E. I. L. E. E. N., Ohls, J., Carlson, S., & Fleming, K. (1995). The healthy eating index: design and applications. *Journal of the American dietetic association*, 95(10), 1103-1108.
- Tae, H., & Kim, T. S. (2024). The effect of prebiotic and probiotic food consumption on anxiety severity: a nationwide study in Korea. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 11, 1385518.
- Tajik, E., Awang, H., Nur'Asyura, A. S., Chin, Y. S., Shah, A. B. A., Koh, C. H. P., & Hariz, C. G. M. I. (2016). Unhealthy diet practice and symptoms of stress and depression among adolescents in Pasir Gudang, Malaysia. *Obesity research & clinical practice*, 10(2), 114-123.
- Takagi, Y., Sakai, Y., Abe, Y., Nishida, S., Harrison, B. J., Martínez-Zalacaín, I., ... & Tanaka, S. C. (2018). A common brain network among state, trait, and pathological anxiety from whole-brain functional connectivity. *Neuroimage*, 172, 506-516.
- Tapsell, L. C., Neale, E. P., Satija, A., & Hu, F. B. (2016). Foods, nutrients, and dietary patterns: interconnections and implications for dietary guidelines. *Advances in nutrition*, 7(3), 445-454.
- Tavakol, M., & Wetzel, A. (2020). Factor Analysis: a means for theory and instrument development in support of construct validity. *International journal of medical education*, 11, 245.
- Tennant, R., Hiller, L., Fishwick, R., Platt, S., Joseph, S., Weich, S., ... & Stewart-Brown, S. (2007). The Warwick-Edinburgh mental well-being scale (WEMWBS): development and UK validation. *Health and Quality of life Outcomes*, 5, 1-13.
- Toader, C., Dobrin, N., Costea, D., Glavan, L. A., Covache-Busuioc, R. A., Dumitrascu, D. I., ... & Ciurea, A. V. (2024). Mind, Mood and Microbiota—Gut–Brain Axis in Psychiatric Disorders. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 25(6), 3340.
- Torabynasab, K., Shahinfar, H., Zeraattalab-Motlagh, S., Jazayeri, S., Effatpanah, M., & Azadbakht, L. (2024). The association of major dietary patterns with odds and severity of anxiety disorders: a case–control study. *Nutritional Neuroscience*, 1-10.
- Tran, N., Zhebrak, M., Yacoub, C., Pelletier, J., & Hawley, D. (2019). The gut-brain relationship: Investigating the effect of multispecies probiotics on anxiety in a randomized placebo-controlled trial of healthy young adults. *Journal of affective disorders*, 252, 271-277.

- Valles-Colomer, M., Falony, G., Darzi, Y., Tigchelaar, E. F., Wang, J., Tito, R. Y., ... & Raes, J. (2019). The neuroactive potential of the human gut microbiota in quality of life and depression. *Nature microbiology*, *4*(4), 623-632.
- van der Pols, J. C. (2018). Nutrition and mental health: Bidirectional associations and multidimensional measures. *Public Health Nutrition*, *21*(5), 829.
- Varni, J. W., Seid, M., & Rode, C. A. (1999). The PedsQL™: measurement model for the pediatric quality of life inventory. *Medical care*, *37*(2), 126-139.
- Vejrup, K., Hillesund, E. R., Agnihotri, N., Helle, C., & Øverby, N. C. (2023). Diet in Early Life Is Related to Child Mental Health and Personality at 8 Years: Findings from the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa). *Nutrients*, *15*(1), 243.
- Vereijken, C. M. J. L., Weenen, H., & Hetherington, M. M. (2011). Feeding infants and young children. From guidelines to practice-conclusions and future directions. *Appetite*, *57*(3), 839-843.
- Walter, H. J., Bukstein, O. G., Abright, A. R., Keable, H., Ramtekkar, U., Ripperger-Suhler, J., & Rockhill, C. (2020). Clinical practice guideline for the assessment and treatment of children and adolescents with anxiety disorders. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, *59*(10), 1107-1124.
- Wang, Y., Liu, J., Compher, C., & Kral, T. V. (2022). Associations between dietary intake, diet quality and depressive symptoms in youth: A systematic review of observational studies. *Health Promotion Perspectives*, *12*(3), 249.
- Waters, A. M., Bradley, B. P., & Mogg, K. (2014). Biased attention to threat in paediatric anxiety disorders (generalized anxiety disorder, social phobia, specific phobia, separation anxiety disorder) as a function of 'distress' versus 'fear' diagnostic categorization. *Psychological medicine*, *44*(3), 607-616.
- Weng, S. F., Redsell, S. A., Swift, J. A., Yang, M., & Glazebrook, C. P. (2012). Systematic review and meta-analyses of risk factors for childhood overweight identifiable during infancy. *Archives of disease in childhood*, *97*(12), 1019-1026.
- Weng, T. T., Hao, J. H., Qian, Q. W., Cao, H., Fu, J. L., Sun, Y., ... & Tao, F. B. (2012). Is there any relationship between dietary patterns and depression and anxiety in Chinese adolescents?. *Public health nutrition*, *15*(4), 673-682.
- Whiteside, S. P., Deacon, B. J., Benito, K., & Stewart, E. (2016). Factors associated with practitioners' use of exposure therapy for childhood anxiety disorders. *Journal of anxiety disorders*, *40*, 29-36.

- WHO. (2021). *Mental health of adolescents*. Wwww.who.int. https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-mental-health/?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAjw74e1BhBnEiwAbqOAJfOrE_xFzUmm2-nYPy7YOvblmJ2NqM_Kt_bGv7W_odsPhAGpkRZxoCXDsQAvD_BwE.
- Wong, O. W., Lam, A. M., Or, B. P., Mo, F. Y., Shea, C. K., Lai, K. Y., ... & Leung, P. W. (2022). Disentangling the relationship of gut microbiota, functional gastrointestinal disorders and autism: a case–control study on prepubertal Chinese boys. *Scientific Reports*, *12*(1), 10659.
- Xiong, R. G., Li, J., Cheng, J., Zhou, D. D., Wu, S. X., Huang, S. Y., ... & Li, H. B. (2023). The role of gut microbiota in anxiety, depression, and other mental disorders as well as the protective effects of dietary components. *Nutrients*, *15*(14), 3258.
- Xu, M. M., Qiu, W. H., Ma, Q. Y., Yu, Z. Y., Yang, W. M., Hu, T. N., ... & Chen, X. Y. (2024). Improving precision management of anxiety disorders: a Mendelian randomization study targeting specific gut microbiota and associated metabolites. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *15*, 1380912.
- Zhuang, L., Chen, H., Zhang, S., Zhuang, J., Li, Q., & Feng, Z. (2019). Intestinal microbiota in early life and its implications on childhood health. *Genomics, Proteomics and Bioinformatics*, *17*(1), 13-25.
- Zijlmans, M. A., Korpela, K., Riksen-Walraven, J. M., de Vos, W. M., & de Weerth, C. (2015). Maternal prenatal stress is associated with the infant intestinal microbiota. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, *53*, 233-245.